

South-East European International Institute for Sustainable Technologies –
SEEIIST

CERN openlab IT-OPL

Capacity building program:

**Large-scale privacy-preserving data analysis platforms for
medical research applications**

Ivan Knežević

Supervisors:

Alberto Di Meglio, PhD

Manjit Dosanjh, MD, PhD

12 months progression report

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Association

1 Introduction

In the recent decades, far-reaching transformations involving data have occurred, especially concerning medical data. The technology has improved radically, became pervasive, and has enabled to generate amount of data never seen before, from multiple sources, because basically every hospital, clinic, or medical center, became a data generating entity.

First, data became big, in terms of size, and new dimensions were defined: the so-called V's (Value, Volume, Veracity, etc.). According to McKinsey Global Institute, the terms of big data identify datasets whose size is beyond the current capability and capacity of a database software to capture, store, manage and analyze data. The global community is mobilizing to create new infrastructures and tools to manage these exploding data volumes.

The Big Data ecosystem is a very powerful instrument for the scientific and medical progress at the global scale, and its infrastructure, governance and reliability remain challenging.

Second, data became open. The term open has been used in many different ways: open software, open data, open research, and, more in general, open content and open knowledge. Even though the concept of openness was first mentioned in the end of the '90s, it still remains a challenging research topic. In particular, the definition of a fair governance and access is on top of European discussions. Open data in medical terms is a very blurry concept, as it is necessary to constantly balance between data privacy, patient confidentiality and data availability.

These recent drastic transformations have highlighted even more than previously the need to change the pace and modality of how medical data is collected, organized, analyzed, and shared at large scale to address critical and urgent medical challenges and support rapid, informed, accountable response mechanisms for governments, organizations and for benefitting patients. One of the identified causes of the lack of global coordination is the difficulty of implementing large-scale, cross-disciplinary investigations able to access large amounts of data from multiple sources. For such investigation to be effective, barriers due to data access, governance, scalability, reproducibility must be overcome. And that very point rapidly became the biggest obstacle for this project.

2 Large-scale privacy-preserving data analysis platforms for medical research applications

Medical data treated in this project are cancer-patients' data from the area of south-east Europe. The SEEIIST¹ project's main goal is the construction of a research center for the treatment of cancer with hadron therapy, i.e., heavy ion therapy, in Southeast Europe. A special component of the project is an education and training platform for young scientists, researchers, technicians, doctors, biologists, biomedical engineers, and others that will contribute to the improvement of the entire region in terms of technological progress, medical innovation, scientific achievements, industrial empowerment, and economic benefits. One of the disciplines that will be studied and applied within this project is the field of artificial intelligence, specifically machine learning - which is also a field of my interest and this research. The aim of the project is to lay the foundations for building an intelligent system that would unify data of all oncology centers from Southeast Europe, and thus create a homogeneous data set that could be used in machine learning, whether it is prediction by classification or regression, supervised or unsupervised method, for eventually selecting patients that would benefit from heavy ion therapy.

Since the data are collected from 10 countries in Southeast Europe, each of which has its own way of collecting and storing data, this makes the data very heterogeneous, and for the data to be used for any further analysis, first, degree of similarity must be established and only then, can the necessary work on data homogenization be started.

Any machine learning predictions of this type are made based on the analysis of a large amount of data from similar patients, and of course, the greater this number, the higher the accuracy of the given prediction. Such analysis is performed on samples of several tens, even hundreds of thousands of patients, and such an amount of data can only be obtained by combining all member countries data repositories, and sharing data with each other, which is one of the goals of the SEEIIST project.

¹ The South East European International Institute for Sustainable Technologies - <https://seeiist.eu/>

3 Goals and report

One of the first requirements of any data analysis and machine learning projects is access to large amount of actual data, and in this particular case cancer patient's data. As process of medical data acquisition could be a long bureaucratic process, it was decided to divide the main goals (G_i) as following:

(G_1) Summarizing the state-of-the-art technologies applicable to the project objectives and their practical use in the process of privacy-preserving medical data analysis.

(G_2) Data acquisition, analysis, and its preparation for machine learning process.

As the cancer patient's data that should have been provided by other member states were missing, despite several requests sent to the SEEIIST board, goals set in the 6 months report had to be changed from:

~~(G_3) Combining and unifying data from different sources and creation of unique dataset.~~

~~(G_4) Creation of machine learning algorithm capable of suggesting patients suitable for hadron therapy.~~

to:

(G_3) Dataset analysis and quantification of categorical data.

(G_4) Federated Learning environment for data acquisition and aggregation.

3.1 Available technologies – CS4OD project

To face the challenges in drastic data transformations in the last decade, CERN started a dedicated project called CERN Science for Open Data (CS4OD). A team of experts select high impacts projects and implement activities that cover areas such as:

- **Data Stewardship and Governance.**
- **Data Repository.**
- **Data Engineering.**
- **Data science.**

Our project is an excellent candidate for CS4OD use-case, as it is a high impact project that implements activities that cover most of the above-mentioned areas.

CERN experts will support the selected projects for an agreed period until they are able to run services and research independently, although CERN might decide to remain involved in some of them for longer periods based on strategic reasons.

CERN has a long, proven track record of open science and of implementing and managing large-scale, data-driven operations. In collaboration with international initiatives and projects, CERN engineers and physicists have over time developed both efficient

strategies for managing data at scale and tools able to support such strategies. Optimized and efficient systems, combined with the experience of implementing distributed systems and a strong culture of openness and sharing ideas, software and data make CERN an obvious partner to implement multi-disciplinary data-driven research projects based on open access data and open-source tools. Some of the tools used during my work at CERN that will also be part of the CS4OD platform are:

- **Zenodo**² data repository (provided by CERN) launched in May 2013 is an open-source catch-all repository for EC funded research created in collaboration with CERN and OpenAIRE project. Zenodo host many different contents, such as software, articles, data and code, and allows to create versions of them. Zenodo bases on FAIR principles (<https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>). Once the content is published, Zenodo issues a DOI. Data can be stored in public or private manner.
- **Binder** (also available with CERN account) is a platform for interactive data analysis in the cloud which allows to create a custom computing environment and bases on docker images and Kubernetes to run and share notebooks with remote users. Several repository accounts can be used to access, for instance GitHub, GitLab and Zenodo.
- **SWAN** (provided by CERN) is a platform for interactive data analysis in the cloud which allows to set a computing environment (among some predefined) and based on docker images and Kubernetes to run and share notebooks with remote users. GitHub account can be used to access. CERNBox is the home directory and synchronize the local user storage with the cloud which gives the possibility to share folders and files. It relies on file system EOS. It is possible to submit jobs to CERN Spark Clusters.
- **Kubernetes** is an open-source container orchestration system for automating computer application deployment, scaling and management. It works with a range of container tools and runs containers in a cluster, often with images built using Docker.

Data orchestration and analysis containerization have a fundamental role in data analysis and deployment, in particular for machine learning applications. Therefore, these tools will be considered for use in our project.

3.2 (*G_I*) Privacy-preserving medical data analysis

Medical data has unique properties that make it extremely challenging to integrate, because data types range from free-text clinical notes and laboratory analysis to heterogeneous medical images. Also, medical data sources themselves are dispersed across different, incompatible systems. Combining these challenges with the privacy concerns around the use of patient data (which has the highest requirements for protection and

² <https://about.zenodo.org>

anonymization) and it becomes clear why it's so hard for traditional machine learning techniques to achieve sufficiently large, real-world data sets that have a shared responsibility towards the data owner: the patient.

Federated learning (FL) is an emerging technique that aims to overcome this issue by keeping patient data private, at source, while sharing only outcomes that don't contain personal information. Separate healthcare information systems send their specific models to a centralized server, where the models are then averaged to obtain a single, combined model. This repeats for several iterations until a high-quality model is obtained.

Figure 1 - Federated learning workflow

The proposal is to develop a machine learning system based on Federated Learning technique capable of training a high-quality model with data distributed over several independent providers. As predictive models need to be trained on heterogeneous data to generalize well to different patient populations and treatment plans, project should start with simple healthcare datasets (datasets already available) of cancer patients, and gradually increase in dataset complexity and ML algorithms used for its analysis. Final result should represent a prediction model capable of suggesting patients suitable for hadron therapy (G_4).

After developing initial training models in the first phase, we will ensure collaboration with different healthcare institutions in project state members willing to share their data and, at the same time, benefit from its use.

Figure 2 - Federated Learning architecture

Federated Learning model should consist of several collaborator workstations, stationed in respective medical institutions, i.e., data holders. Each collaborator in this federation will be controlled by Parameter server, that maintains the current model and regularly distributes it to the workers who in turn calculate a gradient update and send it back to the server. The server then applies all the updates to the central model. This is repeated until the model converges. The workers perform machine learning over their own data and the master merely aggregates the resulting models without seeing any raw data. This way, patient's data never leave their own institution, and only locally trained data are sent to aggregator server and then redistributed to other nodes, while preserving privacy.

3.3 (G_2) Data acquisition and analysis

I started the data collection process first by contacting the Montenegrin representative before SEEIIST, Mara Šćepanović, PhD, as well as a representative of the Oncology Institute in Montenegro, Vladimir Todorović, PhD. I chose Montenegro, as a smallest country, as well as my home country, hoping that it could help me obtain medical data faster. After several contacts with representatives from medical data acquisition entities in Montenegro (Clinical center of Montenegro and Institute for public health of Montenegro), I was introduced to procedure that required writing a formal request and appearing before ethics committee where it was necessary to give a detailed explanation on how data will be acquired, treated, and used, in respect of Personal Data Protection Act. Prof. Mara Šćepanović was of huge help during this process, as she took responsibility to finish all bureaucracy necessary for the entire process.

The entire process lasted over two months, and formal approval from the Ethics committee was given on July 15th. With this approval, I contacted dr Rajko Strahinja from the Institute of public health of Montenegro, who is also head of Registry of Malignant Neoplasms of Montenegro, within Center for Disease prevention and control of NCDs. Since 2012, he has worked intensively on the creation of the Register of Malignant Neoplasms of

Montenegro at the Institute of public health. The register is of the population type at the state level, i.e., collects data for all Montenegrins suffering from cancer, regardless of where the diagnosis of the disease is made and where the treatment is carried out (in Montenegro or abroad). The raw data were sent to the European Network of Cancer Registries (ENCR) and can be found on the institution's website within the ECIS (Electronic Cancer Information System). I received this raw data on July 21st, which gave me a possibility to analyze it in detail.

This registry I received from dr Strahinja, follows strict ENCR data format regulations and in addition to that ENCR are developing data quality-checking (QC) software based on the data quality-check protocol. Dataset is composed of independent cancer incident cases containing following data:

Time period

All available registration years which are considered complete, up to and including, 2013.

Tumor

- All primary malignant Tumors, including basal cell and squamous cell carcinomas of skin;
- All in situ Tumors.
- All uncertain behavior Tumors.
- Benign Tumors of the central nervous system (CNS) and urinary bladder

Multiple primary Tumors

- All multiple primary Tumors are to be retained in the file. Multiple primary Tumors will be defined according to the "International rules for multiple primary cancer (ICD-0 Third Edition)"

Age

- All ages are eligible for registration.
- In age-restricted cancer registries, such as childhood cancer registries, all subsequent primary tumors of the registered patients should be included, if available, irrespective of age at diagnosis.

File format

The file is formatted as follows:

- One record per tumor.
- The file should be a text file with semi colon (;) separators and should include a header, with variables named and order as specified in the text below (including the number and the text) and in Table 1.

1_Flag; 2_Patient_ID; 3_Tumor_ID; 4_Day_DoB; 5_Month_DoB; 6_Year_DoB; 7_Sex;
8_Day_DoI; 9_Month_DoI; 10_Year_DoI; 11_Age; 12_BoD; 13_Topo; 14_Morpho; 15_Beh;
16_Grade; 17_Autopsy; 18_Vital_status; 19_Day_FU; 20_Month_FU; 21_Year_FU;
22_Survival; 23_Laterality; 24_Day_DoR; 25_Month_DoR; 26_Year_DoR; 27_Cause_death;
28_ICD_edition; 29_TNM_prefix; 30_pT; 31_pN; 32_pM; 33_cT; 34_cN; 35_cM; 36_Stage;
37_TNM_edition; 38_Cond_T; 39_Cond_N; 40_Cond_M; 41_Dukes; 42_FIGO; 43_AA Arbor;
44_Gleason; 45_Breslow; 46_EoD; 47_Tsize; 48_N_exam_nodes; 49_N_met_nodes;

50_Sent_nodes; 51_Met_sent_nodes; 52_Cfactor; 53_Surgery; 54_Systemic_th;
55_Radiotherapy; 56_BMtransp.

- Core variables are submitted, for all records, according to the codes detailed in Table 1. Blank codes are not accepted for core variables.
- Additional variables are submitted for all records, if collected. If, in the earlier years, these are not available, the fields should be blank and reports as “unknown”. If the CR does not systematically collect all the additional variables or only some of them, blank fields should be shown.
- All core and additional variables are submitted for all records, whether blank or not, in the order shown in Table 1.

Table 1- Variable number, name, description, format, core/additional, missing/unknown values, and coding schema

Variable name	Variable description	Format	Maximum length	Core	Missing /unknown values	Coding
1_Flag	Check flag	F	1	Y	Not allowed	0 → Not checked 1 → Checked
2_Patient_ID	Patient identification code	A	50	Y	Not allowed	According to registry coding
3_Tumor_ID	Tumor identification	A	50	Y	Not allowed	According to registry coding
4_Day_DoB	Day of birth	F	2	Y	99	Range of allowed values: From 1 to 31
5_Month_DoB	Month of birth	F	2	Y	99	Range of allowed values: From 1 to 12
6_Year_DoB	Year of birth	F	4	Y	9999	Range of allowed values: > 1842 and ≤ the current year
7_Sex	Sex	F	1	Y	9	1 → Male 2 → Female 3 → Other
8_Day_DoI	Day: date of incidence	F	2	Y	99	Range of allowed values: From 1 to 31
9_Month_DoI	Month: date of incidence	F	2	Y	99	Range of allowed values: From 1 to 12
10_Year_DoI	Year: date of incidence	F	4	Y	Not allowed	Range of allowed values: > 1941 and ≤ the current year
11_Age	Age at diagnosis (incidence date) in years	F	3	Y*	999	Range of allowed values: ≥ 0 and < 121

12_BoD	Basis of diagnosis	F	1	Y	9	0→Death certificate only (DCO) 1→Clinical 2→Clinical investigation 4→Specific Tumor markers 5→Cytology 6→Histology of a metastasis 7→Histology of a primary Tumor
13_Topo	Topography (topography of the metastasis is not admitted)	A	4	Y	Not allowed	Valid code in ICD-O-3
14_Morpho	Morphology	F	4	Y	Not allowed	Valid code in ICD-O-3
15_Beh	ICD-O-3 behaviour	F	1	Y	Not allowed	0→ Benign neoplasm 1→ Neoplasm of uncertain and unknown behavior 2→ In-situ neoplasm 3→Malignant neoplasm stated or presumed to be primary
16_Grade	Grade(ICD-O-3)	F	1	Y	9	1→Well differentiated, 2→Moderately differentiated 3 →Poorly differentiated 4→Undifferentiated, anaplastic 5→T-cell; T-precursor 6→B-Cell; Pre-B; B-precursor 7→Null cell; Non T-non B 8→NK cell (natural killer cell)
17_Autopsy	Incidental finding of cancer at autopsy	F	1	Y	9	0→No 1→Yes
18_Vital_status	The last known vital status	F	1	Y	9	1→ Alive 2→ Dead
19_Day_FU	Day of last known vital status	F	2	Y	99	Range of allowed values: From 1 to 31
20_Month_FU	Month of last known vital status	F	2	Y	99	Range of allowed values: From 1 to 12
21_Year_FU	Year of last known vital status	F	4	Y	9999	Range of allowed values: > 1941 and ≤ the current year
22_Survival	Duration of survival in days	F	5	Y***	99999	≥ 0
23_Laterality	Laterality of paired organs	F	1	N	9	0→Not applicable 1→Right 2→Left 3→Unilateral NOS 4→Bilateral

24_Day_DoR	Day of case registration	F	2	N	99	Range of allowed values: From 1 to 31
25_Month_DoR	Month of case registration	F	2	N	99	Range of allowed values: From 1 to 12
26_Year_DoR	Year of case registration	F	4	N	9999	Range of allowed values: > 1941 and ≤ the current year
27_Cause_death	Official underlying cause of death	A	5	N	99999	International Classification of Diseases
28_ICD_edition	ICD edition used for coding cause of death	F	2	N	99	Range of allowed values: ≥ 7 and ≤ 10
29_TNM_prefix	Additional descriptor for TNM	A	1	N	Blank	Prefix modifiers will be considered: y : stage assessed after neo-adjuvant therapy. a : stage determined at autopsy
30_pT	TNM stage, pathological primary site (pT)	A	10	N	9	TNM Classification of Malignant Tumors, 5 th , 6 th or 7 th edition
31_pN	TNM stage, pathological lymph nodes (pN)	A	10	N	9	TNM Classification of Malignant Tumors, 5 th , 6 th or 7 th edition
32_pM	TNM stage, pathological metastases (pM)	A	10	N	9	TNM Classification of Malignant Tumors, 5 th , 6 th or 7 th edition
33_cT	TNM stage, clinical primary site (cT)	A	10	N	9	TNM Classification of Malignant Tumors, 5 th , 6 th or 7 th edition
34_cN	TNM stage, clinical lymph nodes (cN)	A	10	N	9	TNM Classification of Malignant Tumors, 5 th , 6 th or 7 th edition
35_cM	TNM stage, clinical metastases (cM)	A	10	N	9	TNM Classification of Malignant Tumors, 5 th , 6 th or 7 th edition
36_Stage	TNM stage grouping	A	4	N	9	TNM Classification of Malignant Tumors, 5 th , 6 th or 7 th edition
37_TNM_edition	TNM edition	F	2	N	99	Allowed values: 5, 6 and 7
38_Cond_T	Condensed TNM, T	A	2	N	9	TL→Localised TA→Advanced TX→Unknown

39_Cond_N	Condensed TNM, N	A	2	N	9	N0→No regional nodes N1→ Regional nodes NX→Unknown
40_Cond_M	Condensed TNM, M	A	2	N	9	M0→No distant metastasis M1→ Distant metastasis MX→Unknown
41_Dukes	Dukes' stage	A	1	N	9	A→Dukes' stage A B→Dukes' stage B C→Dukes' stage C D→Dukes' stage D 8→not applicable
42_FIGO	FIGO stage	A	5	N	9	0 →FIGO stage 0 1 → FIGO stage I IA → FIGO stage IA IA1 → FIGO stage IA1 IA2 → FIGO stage IA2 IB → FIGO stage IB IB1 → FIGO stage IB1 IB2 → FIGO stage IB2 IC → FIGO stage IC II → FIGO stage II IIA → FIGO stage IIA IIA1 → FIGO stage IIA1 IIA2 → FIGO stage IIA2 IIB→ FIGO stage IIB IIB1→ FIGO stage IIB1 IIB2→ FIGO stage IIB2 IIC→ FIGO stage IIC III → FIGO stage III IIIA → FIGO stage IIIA IIIB→ FIGO stage IIIB IIIC→ FIGO stage IIIC IIIC1→ FIGO stage IIIC1 IIIC2→ FIGO stage IIIC2 IVA→ FIGO stage IVA IVB → FIGO stage IVB 8→not applicable
43_AA Arbor	ANN ARBOR stage	A	4	N	9	Allowed values: I,II,III,IV and suffixes 1,2 (for stage III) suffixes 2-9 (for stage II) 8→not applicable
44_Gleason	GLEASON grading	F	2	N	9	Range of valid values: 1 → Gleason ≤ 6 2→ Gleason =7 3 → Gleason 8-10
45_Breslow	BRESLOW thickness	F	6	N	999.99	Tumor size in mm. >0.00- 900.99

46_EoD	Summary extent of disease	F	1	N	9	1→ Confined 2→ Adjacent tissues, and/or regional lymph-nodes 3→ Distant organs 4→ Not confined but not specified whether code 2 or 3 applies 5→ Not distant metastasis but not specified whether code 1 or 2 applies
47_Tsize	Tumor size in mm	F	3	N	999	Range of allowed values: > 0 or 999
48_N_exam_nodes	Number examined nodes	F	2	N	99	Range of allowed values: From 0 to 99
49_N_met_nodes	Number metastatic nodes	F	2	N	99	Range of allowed values: From 0 to number examined nodes
50_Sent_nodes	Sentinel nodes	F	1	N	9	1 → Done 2 → Not done → Not applicable
51_Met_sent_nodes	Metastatic in sentinel nodes	F	1	N	9	1 → Yes 2 → No → Not applicable
52_Cfactor	C factor	F	1	N	9	1→ C1 Evidence from standard diagnostic methods only 2→ C2 Evidence obtained by special diagnostic means 3→ C3 Evidence from surgical exploration, including biopsy and cytology 4→ C4 Evidence following definitive surgery and pathological examination of the resected specimen 5→ C5 Evidence from autopsy
53_Surgery	Surgery	F	1	N	9	1→ Yes 2→ No
54_Systemic_th	Systemic therapy	F	1	N	9	1→ Yes 2→ No
55_Radiotherapy	Radiotherapy	F	1	N	9	1→ Yes 2→ No
56_BMtransp	Bone marrow transplantation	F	1	N	9	1→ Yes 2→ No

F: Numeric variable; A: Alphanumeric variable Y= yes; N= no

Next step in data analysis consists of data cleaning and making correlation matrix, a table showing correlation coefficients between variables (in this case, columns of the table). Each cell in the table shows the correlation between two variables. A correlation matrix is used to summarize data, as an input into a more advanced analysis, and as a diagnostic for advanced analyses. This is still ongoing process and at this moment haven't produced any significant result.

3.4 (G_3) Dataset analysis and quantification of categorical data

On 18th of August 2021, I wrote an email addressed to the members of SEEIIST Steering Committee, and its chairman, prof. Leonard Litov, where I explained that my research consists of designing a proof-of-concept platform for collaborative learning, that should aggregate all cancer-patients' data from the region of South-East Europe, that later should be used for machine learning purposes, for suggesting and classifying patients suitable for heavy ion treatment. I explained to them that I have found all contacts and institutions in member countries, that SEEIIST representatives from respective countries should contact in order to start procedure for obtaining these data, the same procedure that Montenegro has already done, and I have sent it to Committee members in the attachment of that e-mail. I kindly asked all countries representatives to contact their respective contact persons and institutions indicated in this list, so they can start this procedure, that is different in every country. Unfortunately, by the end of the year, I had not received a response from any member state.

My second request concerns the end results of my research, i.e., final suggestion and classification of patients suitable for heavy ion treatment. As ENCR patient data contain a lot of attributes (their age, sex, type of cancer, morphology, topology, and grade of cancer etc...), we need to know what the criteria are for selecting patients suitable for heavy ion treatment, i.e., which of these attributes are to be considered first, or with higher impact on final results. As this is a very complex oncology issue, I suggested that SEEIIST, as an umbrella institute, contacts institutions that are already dealing with heavy ion therapy in Europe (HIT in Heidelberg (DE), CNAO in Pavia (IT), MIT in Marburg (DE), and MedAustron in Wiener Neustadt (AT)), and ask them if they can help us with this issue, and/or share their methodology for selecting patients. Yet again, I had not received a response from any member state regarding this issue. Fortunately, one of my mentors, dr Manjit Dosanjh have sent me appropriate materials regarding heavy ion therapy and methods for selecting patients in Europe, Japan, and South Korea. Furthermore, she organized 4th Seminar of HITRIplus³ with the topic "CIRT at Medaustron: the first 200 patients" with prof. Piero Fossati, head of the carbon ion program and scientific director of MedAustron, as prime speaker, where I had opportunity to discuss and ask questions regarding their methods for patients' selection. I also tried independently to contact institutions that are already dealing with heavy ion therapy in Europe, and received positive feedback from CNAO (Centro Nazionale di Adroterapia Oncologica) in Pavia, Italy, from which I received few scientific papers regarding the matter of interest. All this helped me in the process of quantification of data, in particularly developing detailed data structure regarding cancer types, which will be displayed in detail in the following section.

³ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1094930/>

3.4.1 CNAO - Hadron therapy: the rational and the clinical indications⁴

Evaluating which patients can benefit from the use of hadrons, keeping in mind that conventional radiotherapy is already today capable of giving effective answers to almost half of patients suffering from cancer, is important. More reason, given the higher costs of facilities producing hadrons with respect to those providing conventional radiotherapy, identifying the pathologies that the National Health Service must address with these innovative therapies is important. This task has been carried out several times by national and international radiation oncologists' communities, with the support of scientific societies, such as the Italian Association of Radiation Oncologists (AIRO). In 2017, hadron therapy was included in the Essential Levels of Care (LEA), even though without the approval of a national fee, which, in fact, still affects the authorization procedures for patients coming from outside the Lombardy region. As a result of these events, the number of patients treated per year, which was growing, began to level off in the last two years. In this aspect, the difficulty of creating a network that efficiently gathers elective hadron therapy patients has a negative impact; furthermore, as indicated above, those patients are mostly affected by relatively rare pathologies. The image in Fig. 3 also shows the incidence of different pathologies, which are, in most cases, radio-resistant tumors for which carbon ions are used.

Figure 3 - Typology and number of patients treated per year

⁴ S. Rossi, *The National Centre for Oncological Hadron therapy (CNAO): Present Status and Future Perspectives*, Journal of the Korean Physical Society, Vol. 77, No. 5, September 2020, pp. 368~372

Table 2 - Typology of patients treated per year at the CNAO

Chordoma and chondrosarcoma	26%
Head and neck carcinoma and adenocarcinoma	22%
Adenoid cystic carcinoma	18%
Sarcoma	11%
Meningioma	7%
Other brain tumor	4%
Ocular melanoma	3%
Pleomorphic adenoma	2%
Mucosal adenoma	2%
Prostate adenocarcinoma	2%
Hepatocellular carcinoma	1%
Pancreatic adenocarcinoma	1%

3.4.2 A Nordic-Baltic perspective on indications for proton therapy with strategies for identification of proper patients⁵

Indications for proton therapy

A principal goal for PT is to reduce treatment related morbidity and enhanced long-term survival is therefore a prerequisite. Patients with incurable cancer and expected short survival should therefore in general not receive protons. Comorbidity is also a feature influencing the indication. For example, in patients suffering from coronary artery disease and ischemic heart failure qualifying for NYHA class IV, the 1-year survival is 60–70%. Such a patient, although suffering from a curable neoplasm, will probably not benefit from protons. Also, in patients with radio-resistant neoplasms, protons may allow escalation of radiation dose and thereby increase the chance of cure without or with only modest increase in morbidity.

Neoplastic entity

Most review papers and guidelines have, on the basis of modest level evidence, pointed at few and relatively narrow indications for proton therapy based on neoplastic entity⁶. Examples are **childhood cancers** and **adult medulloblastoma, meningioma and ependymoma** where PT is often considered beneficial. Tumor entities such as **chordoma**

⁵ Petter Brandal, Kjell Bergfeldt, Ninna Aggerholm-Pedersen, Gloria Bäckström, Irina Kerna, Michael Gubanski, Kirsten Björnlinger, Morten E. Evensen, Maire Kuddu, Erik Pettersson, Marianne Brydøy, Taran P. Hellebust, Einar Dale, Alexander Valdman, Lars Weber & Morten Høyer (2020) A Nordic-Baltic perspective on indications for proton therapy with strategies for identification of proper patients, *Acta Oncologica*, 59:10, 1157-1163, DOI: 10.1080/0284186X.2020.1817977

⁶ De Ruyscher D, Mark Lodge M, Jones B, et al. Charged particles in radiotherapy: a 5-year update of a systematic review. *Radiother Oncol.* 2012;103(1):5–7.

and **chondrosarcoma**, in which the possibility of dose escalation is an important co-factor, are frequently listed as proton therapy indications based on favorable published outcomes. This applies not least to **chordomas and chondrosarcomas in the base of the skull** and the **sacrum** where gross total resection is most often hard to accomplish, whereas chondrosarcomas in other locations are often treated surgically. The possibility of dose escalation is favorable also in the case of carbon ion therapy for **adenoid cystic carcinoma**.

Anatomy, localization, and size of radiotherapy target volume

The high importance of radiotherapy target volume localization is mirrored by its key position in proton therapy literature and guidelines². This is related to the sparing of non-target tissue and a promise for lower toxicity, particularly in the long term, which probably is the main advantage of PT. For targets in the vicinity of an organ at risk (OAR) such as the brain stem, spinal cord, optic apparatus, heart and rectum, protons can be prioritized, and the sparing effect of protons increases with increasing size of the radiotherapy target volume. Lowering the dose to an OAR is of particular interest where radiotherapy dose objectives to the target cannot be met due to constraints related to the OAR. An example of disease sites listed as suitable for proton therapy is given on the next page, which is a part of ASTRO proton beam therapy guidelines⁷.

Age

Proton therapy is generally accepted as a standard of care in radiotherapy for most cancers in **children and young adolescents** based on the life expectancy of reduced risk of severe late effects and secondary cancer⁸. There is a general understanding that the risk of secondary cancer is a function of integral dose to the body, but the steepness of the function and the possibility of a threshold dose for development of secondary cancer have not been clarified. For most organs a higher radiation dose will lead to a higher risk of secondary cancer, with an exception for the thyroid. Use of pencil beam scanned (PBS) protons increases the conformity and reduces the integral body dose and the neutron dose⁹. This will primarily have impact for young patients receiving radiation therapy for **brain, head and neck cancer, lymphoma, truncal sarcoma, breast, and pelvic neoplasms**. Although secondary cancer probably is one of the serious late effects seen, one should also remember that a reduction of the rate and severity of other detrimental late effects such as cognitive decline, cerebro and cardiovascular disease and endocrine dysfunction will be clinically meaningful for young individuals receiving radiotherapy

⁷ American Medical Association. Proton beam therapy model policy. 2017; [cited 2020 Sep 01]. Available from www.astro.org.

⁸ Sakthivel V, Ganesh KM, McKenzie C, et al. Second malignant neoplasm risk after craniospinal irradiation in X-ray-based techniques compared to proton therapy. *Australas Phys Eng Sci Med*. 2019;42(1):201–209

⁹ Schneider U, Hälgl R. The impact of neutrons in clinical proton therapy. *Front Oncol*. 2015;5:235

Second cancer predisposition

The impact of hereditary factors on the risk of developing a secondary cancer after radiation therapy is not clearly understood. However, in case of cancer syndromes such as **Li Fraumeni** and **neurofibromatosis**, which entail a weakened DNA repair ability, radiation is related to excess risk of secondary cancer¹⁰. It is also known that patients treated for **retinoblastoma** and **Ewing sarcoma** have an increased risk of secondary cancer compared to other cancer patients¹¹. Whether this is related to a hitherto unknown cancer predisposition or not is unknown. In patients with these diagnoses or cancer predisposing hereditary syndromes, the body radiation dose should be minimized whenever radiotherapy is indicated – making PT an attractive modality.

Based on previous it is possible to identify two groups of indications for patients' selection for proton/hadron therapy:

Group 1 indications for proton therapy:

- Malignant and benign primary central nervous system tumors
- Advanced (e.g., T4) and/or unresectable head and neck cancers
- Cancers of the paranasal sinuses and other accessory sinuses
- Non-metastatic retroperitoneal sarcomas
- Re-irradiation cases where cumulative critical structure dose would exceed tolerance dose Hepatocellular cancer
- Ocular tumors, including intraocular melanomas
- Tumors that approach or are located at the base of skull, including but not limited to chordomas and chondrosarcomas
- Primary or metastatic tumors of the spine where the spinal cord tolerance may be exceeded with conventional treatment or where the spinal cord has previously been irradiated
- Primary or benign solid tumors in children treated with curative intent and occasional palliative treatment of childhood tumors
- Patients with genetic syndromes making total volume of radiation minimization crucial, such as but not limited to NF-1 patients and retinoblastoma patients

Group 2 indications for proton therapy

- Non-T4 and resectable head and neck cancers
- Non-metastatic prostate cancers
- Breast cancers
- Thoracic malignancies, including non-metastatic primary lung and oesophageal cancers
- Abdominal malignancies, including non-metastatic primary pancreatic, biliary, and adrenal cancers
- Pelvic malignancies, including non-metastatic rectal, anal, bladder and cervical cancers

Group 1 indications are defined based on medical necessity and published clinical data.

Group 2 indications are a list of specified but not complete indications for proton therapy in the context of evidence development

¹⁰ McBride KA, Ballinger ML, Killick E, et al. Li-Fraumeni syndrome: cancer risk assessment and clinical management. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol.* 2014;11(5):260–271

¹¹ Caruso J, Shulman DS, DuBois SG. Second malignancies in patients treated for Ewing sarcoma: A systematic review. *Pediatr Blood Cancer.* 2019;66(11):e27938

3.4.3 Estimation of the medical need for carbon-ion radiotherapy in Korea¹²

According to the Korea National Cancer Incidence Database, 225 343 cancer cases were newly diagnosed in Korea in 2013. Among them, 25 606 patients were assessed as being potentially eligible for carbon-ion RT after considering the clinical attributes indicating carbon-ion RT. Among the 25 606 identified patients, a total of 5008 patients were found to be eligible for carbon-ion RT. For localized liver cancer, prostate, and lung cancers, 12%, 43% and 14%, respectively, of patients were considered to be carbon-ion RT candidates. For pancreatic cancer, we assessed both localized and regional pancreatic cancer cases as being carbon-ion RT candidates, with an adaptation rate of 2%, owing to the fact that clinical trials for pancreatic cancer are still in progress. For colorectal cancer, we considered that 8.4% of patients with pelvic recurrence after curative treatment were realistic candidates for carbon-ion RT. For soft tissue sarcoma in the retroperitoneum or pelvis, 30% of the patients were considered carbon-ion RT candidates. For cases of bone sarcoma in the spine and inoperable bone sarcoma cases, 30% of patients were considered to be carbon-ion RT candidates. For both bone and soft tissue sarcoma cases, data on cancer prevalence were used instead of cancer incidence data, because patients with inoperable bone or soft tissue sarcoma are currently considered to be candidates for carbon-ion RT¹³. For head and neck cancer, we concluded that 10% of patients with localized salivary gland and sinus cancers were realistic candidates for carbon-ion RT. Prostate cancer was estimated to be the most common indication for carbon-ion RT; a total of 2243 prostate cancer patients were estimated to be carbon-ion RT candidates. The second and third most common cancers eligible for carbon-ion RT were bone and soft tissue cancer, and liver cancer, with 930 and 870 patients, respectively, indicated for carbon-ion RT. Taken together, these three cancer types accounted for 80% of the total estimated medical need for carbon-ion RT.

¹² Estimation of the medical need for carbon-ion radiotherapy in Korea, Ilsung Cho, Young Seok Seo, WonGyun Jung and Mi-sook Kim, *Journal of Radiation Research*, Vol. 59, No. 5, 2018, pp. 588–592, doi: 10.1093/jrr/rry046

¹³ Kamada T, Tsujii H, Tsuhi H et al. Efficacy and safety of carbon ion radiotherapy in bone and soft tissue sarcomas. *J Clin Oncol* 2002;20:4466–71.

Table 3 - Number of patients potentially eligible for carbon-ion radiotherapy in Korea

Tumor site	No. of incident cancer cases in Korea (2013) (a)	No. of patients potentially eligible for carbon-ion RT		
		Summary stage	Incidence ratio (%) (b)	Number of patients (a) × (b)/100
Liver	16 192	Localized	45.1 ^a	7309
Prostate	9515	Localized	55.0 ^a	5229
Lung	23 177	Localized	20.4 ^a	4730
Pancreas	5511	Localized, regional	44.8 ^a	2472
Colon and rectum	21 756	Recurrence in the pelvic area after curative treatment	10.0 ^b	2177
Connective and soft tissue	6831 (cancer prevalent cases)	Soft tissue sarcoma in the retroperitoneum or pelvis	30.0 ^b	2052
Bone and articular cartilage	4043 (cancer prevalent cases)	Bone sarcoma in the spine or inoperable cases	26.0 ^b	1051
Salivary glands	462	T1–4N0M0	75.2 ^b	347
Nose, sinuses, etc.	344	T1–4N0M0	70.0 ^c	241
Total				25 606

^a Incidence data from the Korea National Cancer Incidence Database were used to obtain the number of newly diagnosed cancer patients in 2013.

^b Cancer statistics data in Japan referred to the Gunma Heavy Ion Medical Center were also used in this study.

^c The number of patients potentially eligible for carbon-ion radiotherapy was obtained from the product of the number of cancer incidence cases with a specific stage (a) and the corresponding incidence ratio (b)

3.4.4 Carbon Ion Therapy: Cancer type overview

INTRACRANIAL TUMORS

Meningioma

Multiple studies have confirmed the safety and favorable toxicity profile of carbon radiotherapy for intracranial malignancies, with early use focusing on delivering a carbon ion boost following conventional photon or proton therapy¹⁴. A preliminary study at the Heidelberg Ion Therapy Center (HIT) evaluated 10 patients with high-risk meningioma treated with photon-based radiotherapy and a carbon ion boost to a dose of 18 GyE, with local control (LC) of 72% at 7 years.

High Grade Glioma

High grade gliomas are typically radioresistant, with a poor prognosis despite aggressive treatment¹⁵. Because of this, there has been significant interest in using CIRT as a novel treatment strategy for patients with glioma. Mizoe et al. reported on 48 patients treated with 50 Gy of photons followed by a carbon ion boost of 16.8–24.8 GyE in 8 fractions with nimustine hydrochloride. Overall survival was improved in patients receiving a higher carbon boost dose, with a median progression free survival (PFS) of 26 months. Notably, there were few grade 3 or higher acute events and no late grade 3 toxicities¹⁶.

Skull Base Chordoma/Chondrosarcoma

Skull base tumors present a challenge for treatment given their proximities to OARs (Organs at risk). CIRT thus provides a theoretical advantage for treatment. Mizoe et al. reported on three protocols from NIRS, where a dose of 60.8 GyE in 15 fractions was given over 4 weeks. The 5-year LC was 100% without excessive toxicity¹⁷. Further, with a median dose of 60 GyE in 20 fractions, HIT reported on 96 patients with a 70% 5-year LC. Late grade 3 optic neuropathy was seen in 4.1% of patients, and temporal lobe injury in 7.2%¹⁸. In nine patients treated with resection and adjuvant CIRT, the 7-year overall survival (OS) was 85.7% and the 3-year and recurrence free survival (RFS) rate was 70.0%¹⁹.

¹⁴ Wang X, Zhang Q, Zhang H, Gao J, Ran J, Li Q, et al., editors. The Preliminary Results of Carbon Ion Radiotherapy in 60 Patients. ESTRO 35. Turin: Radiotherapy and Oncology (2016).

¹⁵ Adeberg S, Harrabi SB, Verma V, Bernhardt D, Grau N, Debus J, et al. Treatment of meningioma and glioma with protons and carbon ions. *Radiat Oncol.* (2017) 12:193. doi: 10.1186/s13014-017-0924-7

¹⁶ Mizoe JE, Tsujii H, Hasegawa A, Yanagi T, Takagi R, Kamada T, et al. Phase I/II clinical trial of carbon ion radiotherapy for malignant gliomas: combined X-ray radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and carbon ion radiotherapy. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* (2007) 69:390–6. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrobp.2007.03.003

¹⁷ Mizoe JE, Hasegawa A, Takagi R, Bessho H, Onda T, Tsujii H. Carbon ion radiotherapy for skull base chordoma. *Skull Base.* (2009) 19:219–24. doi: 10.1055/s-0028-1114295

¹⁸ Schulz-Ertner D, Karger CP, Feuerhake A, Nikoghosyan A, Combs SE, Jakel O, et al. Effectiveness of carbon ion radiotherapy in the treatment of skull-base chordomas. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* (2007) 68:449–57. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrobp.2006.12.059

¹⁹ Takahashi S, Kawase T, Yoshida K, Hasegawa A, Mizoe JE. Skull base chordomas: efficacy of surgery followed by carbon ion radiotherapy. *Acta Neurochir.* (2009) 151:759–69. doi: 10.1007/s00701-009-0383-5

Uveal Melanoma

Tsuji et al. reported on 59 patients with locally advanced or unfavorably located choroidal melanoma treated at NIRS from 2001 to 2006. Patients were treated with a single anterior field to doses between 60 GyE and 85 GyE, each given in five fractions, with a 3-year LC of 97.4%. Overall, 40% of patients developed neovascular glaucoma, mostly in the high dose group, with three requiring enucleation (5% of all patients)²⁰.

Orbital Tumors

HIT evaluated 24 patients with radioresistant malignant lacrimal gland tumors treated with active raster scanning technique. The median local control was 24 months, with no grade 4 or higher toxicity²¹. NIRS reported on 33 patients with lacrimal gland tumors with extraorbital extension treated to either 57.6 GyE or 64 GyE in 16 fractions. Although there was an 86% ipsilateral eye preservation rate, 36.4% of patients developed grade 4 optic nerve disorder²².

HEAD AND NECK TUMORS

Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma

Early results from HIT reported a 3-year LC rate of 62% for the 21 patients with unfavorable adenoid cystic carcinomas treated with combination photon and CIRT. No grade 3 or 4 toxicities were observed²³. Sixteen patients with locally advanced adenoid cystic carcinoma were enrolled in a phase I/II trial photon and CIRT boost to a dose of 72 GyE. Three-year LC was 64.6% with no patient developing grade 3 or higher complications²⁴.

A sub-analysis of J-CROS 1402 HN patients found a 3-year LC and OS of 81 and 94% with a median dose of 64 GyE in 16 fractions. Two patients experienced late grade 3 toxicity of dysphagia and brain abscess²⁵. A prospective study analyzing 35 patients at Gunma University Heavy Ion Medical Center for non-squamous cell carcinomas of the head and neck showed promising results with patients receiving 64 GyE and 57.6 GyE in 16 fractions, with 3-year LC and OS rates of 93 and 88%, respectively²⁶.

²⁰ Tsuji H, Ishikawa H, Yanagi T, Hirasawa N, Kamada T, Mizoe JE, et al. Carbon-ion radiotherapy for locally advanced or unfavorably located choroidal melanoma: a Phase I/II dose-escalation study. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* (2007) 67:857–62. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrobp.2006.09.022

²¹ Akbaba S, Lang K, Held T, Herfarth K, Rieber J, Plinkert P, et al. Carbonion radiotherapy in accelerated hypofractionated active raster-scanning technique for malignant lacrimal gland tumors: feasibility and safety. *Cancer Manag Res.* (2019) 11:1155–66. doi: 10.2147/CMAR.S190051

²² Hayashi K, Koto M, Ikawa H, Ogawa K, Kamada T. Efficacy and safety of carbon-ion radiotherapy for lacrimal gland carcinomas with extraorbital extension: a retrospective cohort study. *Oncotarget.* (2018) 9:12932–40. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.24390

²³ Schulz-Ertner D, Nikoghosyan A, Thilmann C, Haberer T, Jakel O, Karger C, et al. Results of carbon ion radiotherapy in 152 patients. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* (2004) 58:631–40. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrobp.2003.09.041

²⁴ Schulz-Ertner D, Nikoghosyan A, Jakel O, Haberer T, Kraft G, Scholz M, et al. Feasibility and toxicity of combined photon and carbon ion radiotherapy for locally advanced adenoid cystic carcinomas. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* (2003) 56:391–8. doi: 10.1016/S0360-3016(02)04511-X

²⁵ Hayashi K, Koto M, Demizu Y, Saitoh JI, Suefuji H, Okimoto T, et al. A retrospective multicenter study of carbon-ion radiotherapy for major salivary gland carcinomas: subanalysis of J-CROS 1402 HN. *Cancer Sci.* (2018) 109:1576–82. doi: 10.1111/cas.13558

²⁶ Shirai K, Saitoh JI, Musha A, Abe T, Kobayashi D, Takahashi T, et al. Prospective observational study of carbon-ion radiotherapy for nonsquamous cell carcinoma of the head and neck. *Cancer Sci.* (2017) 108:2039–44. doi: 10.1111/cas.13325

Parotid Gland Tumors

Patients treated for locally advanced parotid gland tumors with CIRT at NIRS showed a 5-year local control of 74.5% and overall survival of 70.1%. Of the 30 patients without facial nerve deficits prior to radiation, 25 continued to have no evidence of radiation induced facial nerve damage²⁷.

Nasopharyngeal Cancer

In particular, nasopharyngeal carcinomas are among the most accepted indications and may benefit the most from particle therapy, as they often abut critical OARs like the brainstem, optic apparatus, and temporal lobes. HIT retrospectively analyzed 26 patients with high risk nasopharyngeal cancer treated with IMRT and carbon ion boost for a cumulative dose of 74 Gy RBE. With a median follow up of 40 months, 60% had a complete response, with 20% demonstrating partial response and 12% stable disease. The 2-year OS, LC, and distant progression-free survival (PFS) rates were 100, 95, and 93%, respectively. Acute grade 3 toxicity was seen in 20% of patients, with 16% developing late grade 3 toxicity. There were no grade 4 or 5 toxicities²⁸. Akbaba et al. described 59 patients with adenoid cystic carcinoma of the nasopharynx treated at the Heidelberg IonBeam Therapy Centers with combination photon and carbon ion boost radiation therapy. Patients were treated to a dose of 50–56 Gy IMRT followed by 18–24 GyE boost with carbon. The 2-year OS and LC were 87 and 83%, with 12% acute and 8% late grade 3 toxicity²⁹.

Sinonasal Cancer

Koto et al. investigated 22 patients with sinonasal adenocarcinoma treated with CIRT either as definitive therapy or following surgery or chemotherapy, with 14 patients receiving 57.6 GyE in 16 fractions and 8 receiving 64.0 GyE in 16 fractions. With a median follow up of 43 months, the 3-year LC and OS were 76.9 and 59.1%, respectively. Notably, five patients experienced lateral vision loss. Symptomatic brain necrosis and mucosal ulceration were observed in one patient each, respectively³⁰.

Otic Cancer

Primary otic tumors are extremely rare with a poor prognosis, with surgery the mainstay of treatment. JCROS evaluated 31 patients treated for external auditory canal or middle ear carcinomas, with a median dose of 64 GyE in 15 fractions. Three-year OS was 58.7% with similar LC rates. Grade 3 dermatitis was seen in 9.7% of patients, with central nervous

²⁷ Koto M, Hasegawa A, Takagi R, Ikawa H, Naganawa K, Mizoe JE, et al. Definitive carbon-ion radiotherapy for locally advanced parotid gland carcinomas. *Head Neck*. (2017) 39:724–9. doi: 10.1002/hed.24671

²⁸ Akbaba S, Held T, Lang K, Forster T, Federspil P, Herfarth K, et al. Bimodal radiotherapy with active raster-scanning carbon ion radiotherapy and intensity-modulated radiotherapy in high-risk nasopharyngeal carcinoma results in excellent local control. *Cancers*. (2019) 11:E379. doi: 10.3390/cancers11030379

²⁹ Akbaba S, Ahmed D, Lang K, Held T, Mattke M, Hoerner-Rieber J, et al. Results of a combination treatment with intensity modulated radiotherapy and active raster-scanning carbon ion boost for adenoid cystic carcinoma of the minor salivary glands of the nasopharynx. *Oral Oncol*. (2019) 91:39–46. doi: 10.1016/j.oraloncology.2019.02.019

³⁰ Koto M, Hasegawa A, Takagi R, Sasahara G, Ikawa H, Mizoe JE, et al. Feasibility of carbon ion radiotherapy for locally advanced sinonasal adenocarcinoma. *Radiother Oncol*. (2014) 113:60–5. doi: 10.1016/j.radonc.2014.09.009

system (CNS) necrosis in 6.5%. There were no grade 4 or 5 toxicities³¹. Further, NIRS reported on 13 patients with a 3-year LC of 56.4% and OS of 41.6%. Two patients had severe temporal bone necrosis, and four patients developed grade 1–2 localized brain necrosis³².

Oral Cancer

In a large retrospective series, Ikawa et al. analyzed 76 patients with non-squamous oral cavity cancers treated across four institutions in Japan from 2004 and 2014. Forty-six patients had salivary gland carcinoma and 27 had mucosal melanoma. With a median follow up of 31.1 months, the 3-year LC, PFS, and OS were 86.6, 63.1, and 78.4%, respectively. Thirteen patients had late grade 3 or higher toxicity, with 9 patients having grade 3 osteoradionecrosis. There were no grade 5 toxicities. The authors conclude that carbon ion radiotherapy is effective with “acceptable” toxicity for oral cavity cancers³³.

LUNG TUMORS

Non-small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC)

Dosimetric studies have shown lower OAR doses and a more homogenous target dose for NSCLC with CIRT compared to photon, potentially allowing for hypofractionation without increasing toxicity³⁴. In localized disease, Miyamoto et al. described 47 patients in a dose escalation trial with doses from 59.4 to 95.4 GyE. Grade 3 radiation pneumonitis occurred in three patients, although this was not dose limiting as defined by the protocol³⁵. Hypofractionation was then attempted to a dose of 72 GyE in 9 fractions, with a 94.7% LC rate and no grade 4–5 toxicity³⁶. In a second hypofractionation study, patients with stage IA were treated to 42.8 GyE and stage IB to 60.0 GyE in four fractions. The local control was 98% for T1 and 80% for T2 tumors. No grade 4 or 5 lung toxicities were seen³⁷. Single fraction CIRT appears to be feasible for early stage NSCLC with LC of 95% at 5 years with doses above 48 GyE³⁸.

³¹ Hayashi K, Koto M, Demizu Y, Saitoh JI, Suefuji H, Okimoto T, et al. A retrospective multicenter study of carbon-ion radiotherapy for external auditory canal and middle ear carcinomas. *Cancer Med.* (2019) 8:51–7. doi: 10.1002/cam4.1830

³² Koto M, Hasegawa A, Takagi R, Sasahara G, Ikawa H, Mizoe JE, et al. Carbon ion radiotherapy for locally advanced squamous cell carcinoma of the external auditory canal and middle ear. *Head Neck.* (2016) 38:512–6. doi: 10.1002/hed.23905

³³ Ikawa H, Koto M, Demizu Y, Saitoh JI, Suefuji H, Okimoto T, et al. Multicenter study of carbon-ion radiation therapy for nonsquamous cell carcinomas of the oral cavity. *Cancer Med.* (2019) 8:5482–91. doi: 10.1002/cam4.2408

³⁴ Kubo N, Saitoh JI, Shimada H, Shirai K, Kawamura H, Ohno T, et al. Dosimetric comparison of carbon ion and X-ray radiotherapy for Stage IIIA non-small cell lung cancer. *J Radiat Res.* (2016) 57:548–54. doi: 10.1093/jrr/rrw041

³⁵ Miyamoto T, Yamamoto N, Nishimura H, Koto M, Tsujii H, Mizoe JE, et al. Carbon ion radiotherapy for stage I non-small cell lung cancer. *Radiother Oncol.* (2003) 66:127–40. doi: 10.1016/S0167-8140(02)00367-5

³⁶ Miyamoto T, Baba M, Yamamoto N, Koto M, Sugawara T, Yashiro T, et al. Curative treatment of Stage I non-small-cell lung cancer with carbon ion beams using a hypofractionated regimen. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* (2007) 67:750–8. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrobp.2006.10.006

³⁷ Miyamoto T, Baba M, Sugane T, Nakajima M, Yashiro T, Kagei K, et al. Carbon ion radiotherapy for stage I non-small cell lung cancer using a regimen of four fractions during 1 week. *J Thorac Oncol.* (2007) 2:916–26. doi: 10.1097/JTO.0b013e3181560a68

³⁸ Yamamoto N, Miyamoto T, Nakajima M, Karube M, Hayashi K, Tsuji H, et al. A dose escalation clinical trial of single-fraction carbon ion radiotherapy for peripheral stage I non-small cell lung cancer. *J Thorac Oncol.* (2017) 12:673–80. doi: 10.1016/j.jtho.2016.12.012

GASTROINTESTINAL TUMORS

Esophageal Cancer

CIRT has been used successfully in the treatment of squamous cell carcinoma of the esophagus. In a phase I/II trial, 31 patients with resectable disease received between 28.8 and 36.8 GyE in 8 fractions given 4 fractions per week. A 38.7% pathologic complete response rate and 41.9% clinical partial response rate were seen³⁹.

Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC)

In Japan, two protocols (9603 and 0004) attempted hypofractionated treatment for HCC. 52.8 GyE in 4 fractions was the recommended dose, with a 5-year LC of 90%⁴⁰. Recent studies have attempted further dose-escalation, with 48.0–60 GyE given in 4 treatments. All doses had favorable LC and survival rates. Notably, 5.7% had grade 3–4 toxicity with 1.7% developing radiation induced liver disease⁴¹. Given the safety of the four fraction regimens, these were applied to 21 patients with HCC lesions >3 cm, with similar LC and toxicity rates⁴². Further, treatment with 15 fractions in patients with cirrhosis did not increase the Child-Pugh score by more than 2 points⁴³. Patients treated with 52.8 GyE in 4 fractions had no difference in OS or LC based on if the tumor was within 2 cm of the porta hepatis⁴⁴. There was also no difference in toxicity. Given this, the hypofractionated course is felt to be safe for treating in close proximity to the portal system.

Liver Metastases

Makishima et al. found a 3-year LC rate of 82% for single fraction treatment for colorectal cancer liver metastasis at doses above 53 GyE, compared to 28% at lower doses. In contrast to the above study, there were two cases of grade 3 liver toxicity at 53 GyE, with both cases occurring near the hepatic portal region. The authors conclude that single fraction therapy is safe up to 58 GyE if the central hepatic portal region can be avoided⁴⁵.

Cholangiocarcinoma

The Japan Carbon Ion Radiation Oncology Study Group (J-CROS) investigated the role of CIRT for 56 patients with intrahepatic (27 patients) and perihilar (29 patients) cholangiocarcinoma. No patients underwent resection. Most patients were treated to a dose of 76 GyE in 20 fractions, with a median survival of 23.8 months for intrahepatic

³⁹ Akutsu Y, Yasuda S, Nagata M, Izumi Y, Okazumi S, Shimada H, et al. A phase I/II clinical trial of preoperative short-course carbon-ion radiotherapy for patients with squamous cell carcinoma of the esophagus. *J Surg Oncol.* (2012) 105:750–5. doi: 10.1002/jso.22127

⁴⁰ Kasuya G, Kato H, Yasuda S, Tsuji H, Yamada S, Haruyama Y, et al. Progressive hypofractionated carbon-ion radiotherapy for hepatocellular carcinoma: combined analyses of 2 prospective trials. *Cancer.* (2017) 123:3955–65. doi: 10.1002/cncr.30816

⁴¹ Shibuya K, Ohno T, Terashima K, Toyama S, Yasuda S, Tsuji H, et al. Short-course carbon-ion radiotherapy for hepatocellular carcinoma: a multi-institutional retrospective study. *Liver Int.* (2018) 38:2239–47. doi: 10.1111/liv.13969

⁴² Shibuya K, Ohno T, Katoh H, Okamoto M, Shiba S, Koyama Y, et al. A feasibility study of high-dose hypofractionated carbon ion radiation therapy using four fractions for localized hepatocellular carcinoma measuring 3 cm or larger. *Radiother Oncol.* (2019)

⁴³ Kato H, Tsujii H, Miyamoto T, Mizoe JE, Kamada T, Tsuji H, et al. Results of the first prospective study of carbon ion radiotherapy for hepatocellular carcinoma with liver cirrhosis. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* (2004) 59:1468–76. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrobp.2004.01.032

⁴⁴ Imada H, Kato H, Yasuda S, Yamada S, Yanagi T, Kishimoto R, et al. Comparison of efficacy and toxicity of short-course carbon ion radiotherapy for hepatocellular carcinoma depending on their proximity to the porta hepatis. *Radiother Oncol.* (2010) 96:231–5. doi: 10.1016/j.radonc.2010.05.019

⁴⁵ Makishima H, Yasuda S, Isozaki Y, Kasuya G, Okada N, Miyazaki M, et al. Single fraction carbon ion radiotherapy for colorectal cancer liver metastasis: a dose escalation study. *Cancer Sci.* (2019) 110:303–9. doi: 10.1111/cas.13872

cholangiocarcinoma and 12.6 months in perihilar disease. Notably, there was one case of grade 5 liver injury and one grade 3 bile duct stenosis⁴⁶.

Pancreatic Cancer

Shinoto et al. evaluated the safety and efficacy of short course, neoadjuvant irradiation with CIRT for potentially resectable pancreatic cancer. The dose given was escalated from 30 to 36.8 GyE in 8 fractions, with surgery performed up to 4 weeks after completion of radiation. Sixty-five percentage of the 28 patients developed distant disease, with no patients experiencing local recurrence. One patient developing acute grade 3 liver toxicity and one patient developing late grade 4 portal vein stenosis⁴⁷. The J-CROS Study 1403 retrospectively analyzed 72 patients from three institutions with locally advanced pancreatic adenocarcinoma and treated with CIRT to a dose of 52.8 GyE or 55.2 GyE in 12 fractions. The median OS was 21.5 months. The 2-year local recurrence rate was 24%. Twenty-six percentage of patients experienced grade 3 or four hematologic toxicities with 3% grade 3 anorexia⁴⁸.

Rectal Cancer

Patients with a rectal cancer recurrence following primary curative intent therapy were treated with a dose of 73.6 Gy RBE in 16 fractions as part of the GUNMA 0801 prospective study⁴⁹. The 3-year OS, LC, and PFS for the 28 patients were 92, 86, and 31%, respectively. Similarly, the JCROS experience found that patients treated to 70.4 GyE or 73.6 GyE in 16 fractions for recurrent rectal cancer had 5-year OS rates of 51% and LC of 88%. Three patients had grade 3 toxicity with no grade 4 or 5 toxicities⁵⁰.

GENITOURINARY TUMORS

Prostate Cancer

J-CROS 1501 PR was the first multi-institutional observation study (NIRS, Gunma, and the Ion Beam Therapy Center in Saga, Japan) analyzing outcomes of prostate cancer patients treated with CIRT. Fifty-six percentage were high risk, 31% intermediate risk, and 12% were low risk. The 5-year biochemical relapse free survival (bRFS) rates were 99, 100, and 100%, respectively⁵¹. SPHIC investigated 64 patients with localized prostate cancer treated to a dose

⁴⁶ Kasuya G, Terashima K, Shibuya K, Toyama S, Ebner DK, Tsuji H, et al. Carbon-ion radiotherapy for cholangiocarcinoma: a multi-institutional study by and the Japan carbon-ion radiation oncology study group (J-CROS). *Oncotarget*. (2019) 10:4369–79. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.27028

⁴⁷ Shinoto M, Yamada S, Yasuda S, Imada H, Shioyama Y, Honda H, et al. Phase 1 trial of preoperative, short-course carbon-ion radiotherapy for patients with resectable pancreatic cancer. *Cancer*. (2013) 119:45– 51. doi: 10.1002/cncr.27723

⁴⁸ Kawashiro S, Yamada S, Okamoto M, Ohno T, Nakano T, Shinoto M, et al. Multi-institutional Study of carbon-ion radiotherapy for locally advanced pancreatic cancer: japan carbon-ion radiation oncology study group (JCROS) study 1403 pancreas. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. (2018) 101:1212– 21. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrobp.2018.04.057

⁴⁹ Shiba S, Okamoto M, Kiyohara H, Ohno T, Kaminuma T, Asao T, et al. Prospective observational study of high-dose carbon-ion radiotherapy for pelvic recurrence of rectal cancer (GUNMA 0801). *Front Oncol*. (2019) 9:702. doi: 10.3389/fonc.2019.00702

⁵⁰ Shinoto M, Yamada S, Okamoto M, Shioyama Y, Ohno T, Nakano T, et al. Carbon-ion radiotherapy for locally recurrent rectal cancer: Japan carbonion radiation oncology study group (J-CROS) study 1404 rectum. *Radiother Oncol*. (2019) 132:236–40. doi: 10.1016/j.radonc.2018.10.007

⁵¹ Nomiya T, Tsuji H, Kawamura H, Ohno T, Toyama S, Shioyama Y, et al. A multi-institutional analysis of prospective studies of carbon ion radiotherapy for prostate cancer: a report from the Japan carbon ion radiation oncology study group (J-CROS). *Radiother Oncol*. (2016) 121:288– 93. doi: 10.1016/j.radonc.2016.10.009

between 59.2 and 66 GyE in 16–24 fractions without nodal irradiation. Urinary irritation declined temporarily, with quality of life scores returning to baseline at 1 year. The rates of acute grade 1 and 2 genitourinary (GU) toxicity were 20.3 and 10.9%, respectively. Late grade 1 and grade 2 GU toxicity were 3.1 and 1.6%, respectively. Notably, there was a 0% rate of late GI toxicity⁵².

Renal Cell Carcinoma

CIRT has been used with good efficacy and safety for the treatment of primary renal cell carcinoma. The NIRS experience reported on 19 patients treated with 12 or 16 fractions CIRT, with 5-year cancer specific survival (100%) and LC rates (94.1%)⁵³. A non-randomized phase I/II study determined that 72 GyE was well-tolerated, with no dose limiting toxicity. Cancer specific survival rates and LC were 100% with a median follow up of 43.1 months⁵⁴.

SARCOMA

Osteosarcoma

Osteosarcomas of the trunk are traditionally challenging to treat, as surgical resection can lead to significant morbidity. Given this, Matsunobu et al. retrospectively analyzed 78 patients with medically inoperable osteosarcoma of the trunk treated with CIRT to a median dose of 70.4 GyE in 16 fractions over 4 weeks. The 5-year LC and OS were 62 and 33%, respectively. Three patients required skin grafts, although there were no other severe late toxicities. Eight out of nine patients (89%) who were disease free for 5 years were able to ambulate with or without a walker⁵⁵.

Extremity Sarcoma

CIRT has also been studied in localized primary sarcomas of the extremities. A phase I/II study enrolled 17 patients with either primary or recurrent disease and were treated to 52.8, 64, or 70.4 GyE in 13–16 fractions. LC and OS at 5 years was 76 and 56%, respectively. One patient had a femoral fracture, with no other grade 3 or higher late reactions⁵⁶. In a dose escalation study, Kamada et al. found a high rate of grade 3 acute skin reactions (7/17 patients) with 73.6 GyE, and dose escalation was stopped at that time⁵⁷.

⁵² Zhang Y, Li P, Yu Q, Wu S, Chen X, Zhang Q, et al. Preliminary exploration of clinical factors affecting acute toxicity and quality of life after carbon ion therapy for prostate cancer. *Radiat Oncol.* (2019) 14:94. doi: 10.1186/s13014-019-1303-3

⁵³ Kasuya G, Tsuji H, Nomiya T, Makishima H, Haruyama Y, Kobashi G, et al. Updated long-term outcomes after carbon-ion radiotherapy for primary renal cell carcinoma. *Cancer Sci.* (2018) 109:2873–80. doi: 10.1111/cas.13727

⁵⁴ Kasuya G, Tsuji H, Nomiya T, Makishima H, Haruyama Y, Kobashi G, et al. Prospective clinical trial of 12-fraction carbon-ion radiotherapy for primary renal cell carcinoma. *Oncotarget.* (2019) 10:76–81. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.26539

⁵⁵ Matsunobu A, Imai R, Kamada T, Imaizumi T, Tsuji H, Tsujii H, et al. Impact of carbon ion radiotherapy for unresectable osteosarcoma of the trunk. *Cancer.* (2012) 118:4555–63. doi: 10.1002/cncr.27451

⁵⁶ Sugahara S, Kamada T, Imai R, Tsuji H, Kameda N, Okada T, et al. Carbon ion radiotherapy for localized primary sarcoma of the extremities: results of a phase I/II trial. *Radiother Oncol.* (2012) 105:226–31. doi: 10.1016/j.radonc.2012.09.010

⁵⁷ Kamada T, Tsujii H, Tsuji H, Yanagi T, Mizoe JE, Miyamoto T, et al. Efficacy and safety of carbon ion radiotherapy in bone and soft tissue sarcomas. *J Clin Oncol.* (2002) 20:4466–71. doi: 10.1200/JCO.2002.10.050

Sacral Chordoma

A total of 95 patients with medically inoperable sacral chordoma were treated in Japan between 1996 and 2007. The carbon ion dose ranged from 52.8 to 73.6 GyE, with a median dose of 70.4 GyE over 16 fractions. The OS at 5 years was 86% with a LC rate of 88%. Ninety-one percentage of patients were able to ambulate without aide. Of note, two patients required skin grafts and 15 had severe sciatic nerve complications requiring indefinite medications⁵⁸.

CUTANEOUS TUMORS

Skin Cancer

In a Chinese series, 45 patients with squamous cell carcinoma (16 patients), basal cell carcinoma (12 patients), melanoma (8 patients), Bowen's disease (8 patients), or Paget's disease (2 patients) were treated with various dosages. Non-melanoma skin cancers were treated with 60–70 GyE, melanoma 61–75 GyE, Bowen's disease 60 GyE, and Paget's 42.5 GyE over 6–11 fractions. CIRT had favorable local control rates at 1 year, ranging from 80 to 90% for all histologies⁵⁹.

Keloids

CIRT has been successfully used as adjuvant therapy in the treatment of keloids. In a case series from China, 16 patients with keloids were treated postoperatively with 16 GyE in 8 fractions. A 95% success rate was achieved with a mean follow up of 29.7 months. There was no grade 3 or higher toxicities⁶⁰.

BREAST CANCER

There is currently a lack of clinical data investigating the use of CIRT in breast cancer. To date, there are no large clinical trials using CIBT. In a phase I dose escalation study, Karasawa et al. analyzed 7 patients who underwent CIBT who then underwent tumor excision for pathologic evaluation. Three patients received 48 GyE, three received 52.8 GyE, and one received 60.0 GyE. All patients were treated in four fractions and were treated supine with cast and thermoplastic immobilization. Four patients had acute grade 1 skin toxicity, with no other reported acute toxicity. At 3 months, most patients experienced some pathologic response to treatment, although the authors concluded that 3 months was not sufficient to fully evaluate treatment response⁶¹.

⁵⁸ Imai R, Kamada T, Sugahara S, Tsuji H, Tsujii H. Carbon ion radiotherapy for sacral chordoma. *Br J Radiol.* (2011) 84 Spec No 1:S48–54. doi: 10.1259/bjr/13783281

⁵⁹ Zhang H, Li S, Wang XH, Li Q, Wei SH, Gao LY, et al. Results of carbon ion radiotherapy for skin carcinomas in 45 patients. *Br J Dermatol.* (2012) 166:1100–6. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2133.2011.10764.x

⁶⁰ Chen Y, Dong F, Wang X, Xue J, Zhang H, Gao L, et al. Postoperative carbon ion radiotherapy for keloids: a preliminary report of 16 cases and review of the literature. *Wounds.* (2014) 26:264–72.

⁶¹ Karasawa K, Omatsu T, Arakawa A, Yamamoto N, Ishikawa T, Saito M, et al. A Phase I clinical trial of carbon ion radiotherapy for Stage I breast cancer: clinical and pathological evaluation. *J Radiat Res.* (2019) 60:342–7. doi: 10.1093/jrr/rry113

GYNECOLOGIC CANCER

Cervical Cancer

In a systematic review of eight clinical studies from NIRS, Wang et al. concluded that carbon ion radiotherapy is safe and effective in the treatment for gynecologic cancers. The authors found lower rates of local recurrence at doses higher than 70 GyE for cervical cancer⁶². A pooled analysis of protocols 9403 and 9702 evaluated 44 patients with stage IIIB and IVA disease between 1995 and 2000 receiving CIRT for locally advanced cervical carcinoma. Patients received 16 fractions to the whole pelvis followed by a boost of 8 fractions to a dose up to 72.0 GyE. The most severe GI toxicity occurred at doses above 60 GyE, and the authors concluded that the dose to the intestines should be limited to 60 GyE⁶³. In the NIRS protocol 9902, no patient treated with 72.0 GyE failed locally⁶⁴.

Endometrial Cancer

In a pooled analysis of protocols 9704 and 9404 from NIRS, the authors found that the 5-year LC and OS were 86 and 68%, respectively. Of note, inclusion criteria included inoperable and previously untreated stage I–III endometrial carcinoma without para-aortic nodal metastasis. Radiation was given to the whole pelvis with CIRT to a dose of 36.0 GyE in 12 fractions followed by a CIRT boost to a total dose of 62.4–74.4 GyE in 20 fractions with no brachytherapy boost. Notably, the GI tract dose was limited to no more than 60 GyE. No patients experienced grade 3 or higher acute or late toxicity⁶⁵.

PEDIATRIC CANCER

Out of a group of 394 patients treated with CIRT in Germany between 1997 and 2007 for skull base tumors, 17 patients were under the age of 21. The primary tumor was treated in 14 patients, and three patients had recurrent tumors. Patients were treated to a dose of 60 GyE using the raster scan technique. With a median follow up of 49 months, there were no severe side effects. Only one patient experienced tumor progression from a chordoma after 5 years⁶⁶.

NIRS retrospectively reviewed 26 patients from 11 to 20 years old with inoperable osteosarcoma of the trunk. A median of 70.4 GyE in 16 fractions was delivered. A promising

⁶² Wang L, Wang X, Zhang Q, Ran J, Geng Y, Feng S, et al. Is there a role for carbon therapy in the treatment of gynecological carcinomas? A systematic review. *Future Oncol.* (2019). 15:3081–95. doi: 10.2217/fon-2019-0187

⁶³ Kato S, Ohno T, Tsujii H, Nakano T, Mizoe JE, Kamada T, et al. Dose escalation study of carbon ion radiotherapy for locally advanced carcinoma of the uterine cervix. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* (2006) 65:388–97. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrobp.2005.12.050

⁶⁴ Wakatsuki M, Kato S, Ohno T, Karasawa K, Ando K, Kiyohara H, et al. Dose escalation study of carbon ion radiotherapy for locally advanced squamous cell carcinoma of the uterine cervix (9902). *Gynecol Oncol.* (2014) 132:87–92. doi: 10.1016/j.ygyno.2013.10.021

⁶⁵ Irie D, Okonogi N, Wakatsuki M, Kato S, Ohno T, Karasawa K, et al. Carbon ion radiotherapy for inoperable endometrial carcinoma. *J Radiat Res.* (2018) 59:309–15. doi: 10.1093/jrr/rry003

⁶⁶ Combs SE, Kessel K, Habermehl D, Haberer T, Jakel O, Debus J. Proton and carbon ion radiotherapy for primary brain tumors and tumors of the skull base. *Acta Oncol.* (2013) 52:1504–9. doi: 0.3109/0284186X.2013.818255

⁶⁷ Combs SE, Nikoghosyan A, Jaekel O, Karger CP, Haberer T, Munter MW, et al. Carbon ion radiotherapy for pediatric patients and young adults treated for tumors of the skull base. *Cancer.* (2009) 115:1348–55. doi: 10.1002/cncr.24153

LC was also reported, at 62.9% at 5 years, with four patients developing grade 3 or higher late toxicities. Only one patient was unable to ambulate after treatment⁶⁸.

CIRT may provide a particularly important benefit in the pediatric population. As noted in the setting of prostate cancer, CIRT appears to have a lower rate of second malignancies compared to photons. Furthermore, the measured dose ambient dose equivalent for passive scatter carbon beams is lower than passive scattering beams for protons⁶⁹. This property, in combination with a lower neutron dose in active scanning beams compared with IMRT or passive scattering CIRT, may contribute to a lower secondary malignancy rate with CIRT

3.4.5 Quantification of cancer type data

From the entire ENCR dataset, only 12 attributes were selected for correlation matrix analysis (with column 45_Breslow excluded because missing from the Montenegrin dataset). As said before, most of the data in ENCR dataset are categorical data, and not very suitable for correlation analysis, which resulted with inconclusive results.

	7_Sex	11_Age	12_BoD	14_Morpho	15_Beh	16_Grade	18_Vital_status	22_Survival	46_EoD	53_Surgery	54_Systemic_th	55_Radiotherapy
7_Sex												
11_Age	-0.12											
12_BoD	0.04	-0.22										
14_Morpho	0.04	-0.21	0.11									
15_Beh	-0.07	0.11	0.18	-0.09								
16_Grade	-0.06	0.07	-0.21	-0.09	-0.11							
18_Vital_status	-0.15	0.25	-0.37	-0.12	0.11	0.06						
22_Survival	-0.01	-0.07	0.17	0.08	0.03	-0.04	0.13					
46_EoD	-0.04	0.08	-0.22	0.13	-0.02	0.10	0.18	-0.07				
53_Surgery	-0.13	0.15	-0.38	0.09	0.02	0.08	0.39	-0.09	0.40			
54_Systemic_th	-0.01	0.20	-0.21	-0.32	-0.15	0.10	0.03	-0.14	0.09	-0.12		
55_Radiotherapy	-0.09	0.14	-0.16	0.00	-0.08	0.05	0.05	-0.09	0.16	0.03	0.35	

Figure 4 - Correlation matrix of considered data

The only relevant data visible from the table are, more or less, already known, like for example correlation between surgical treatment and survivability of the patients, or correlation between patient vital status and his age. One interesting correlation is visible between surgical treatment of the cancer and the extent of the disease (EoD), where after thorough analysis we can note that surgery was performed mainly on patients whose tumor was confined or has extended to adjacent tissues.

68 Mohamad O, Imai R, Kamada T, Nitta Y, Araki N, Working Group for Bone and Soft Tissue Sarcoma. Carbon ion radiotherapy for inoperable pediatric osteosarcoma. *Oncotarget*. (2018) 9:22976–85. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.25165

69 Yonai S, Matsufuji N, Akahane K. Monte Carlo study of out-of-field exposure in carbon-ion radiotherapy with a passive beam: organ doses in prostate cancer treatment. *Phys Med*. (2018) 51:48–55. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmp.2018.04.391

Based on previous chapters, in order to quantify categorical data, as cancer type, a table has been created. In order to decide on weight and bias of the cancer-type input neuron, four attributes have been taken into consideration:

Number of patients treated (NP), that should give weight on other attributes,

Dose strength (DS), expressed in Gray Equivalent (a dose quantity representing the stochastic health effects of low levels of ionizing radiation on the human body which represents the probability of radiation-induced cancer and genetic damage.),

Local control rate (LC), percentage of a tumor volume equal to or less than the tumor volume at start of radiotherapy,

Overall Survival (OS), percentage of patients that survived at least 3 years (where available) after treatment. Patients with OS of 5 year or more are considered “cured”.

Table 4 - Quantification of the cancer type data and additional relevant data

Tumor type	Sub-type	No Patients treated	Dose strength (GyE)	Local control rate	Overall Survival
INTRACRANIAL TUMORS					
Meningioma		10	18	72,00%	75%
High Grade Glioma		48	50 (photon) 16.8–24.8 (carbon)	N/A	N/A
Skull Base Chordoma/Chondrosarcoma		96	60	70,00%	86.7%
Uveal Melanoma		59	50-85	97.4%	88.2%
Orbital Tumors		24	50-54	93,00%	96%
HEAD AND NECK TUMORS					
Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma	Unfavourable adenoid cystic carcinomas (photon + CIRT)	21	60	62,00%	75,00%
	Locally advanced adenoid cystic carcinoma	16	72	81,00%	94,00%
	Non-squamous cell carcinomas of the head and neck	35	57.6 - 64	93,00%	88,00%
Parotid Gland Tumors		30	57.6-64	74.5%	70.1%
Nasopharyngeal Cancer	High risk nasopharyngeal cancer	26	74	95,00%	100,00%
	Adenoid cystic carcinoma of the nasopharynx	59	50-56 (proton) 18–24 (carbon)	83,00%	87,00%
Sinonasal Cancer	-	22	57.6 - 64	76.9%	59.1%
Otic Cancer	-	31	64	58.7%	58.7%
	-	13	57.6 - 64	56.4%	41.6%
Oral Cancer	Salivary gland carcinoma	46	64	86.6%	90.8%
	Mucosal melanoma	27	64	93.3%	62,00%

LUNG TUMORS					
Non-small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC)	Localized disease	47	59.4 - 95.4		
	Hypofractionation		72	94.7%	
	Hypofractionation on IA stage		42.8	98% for T1	N/A
	Hypofractionation on IB stage		60	80% for T2	
GASTROINTESTINAL TUMORS					
Esophageal Cancer		31	28.8 - 36.8	80.6%	81,00%
Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC)		174	48 - 52.8 - 60	87.77%	83.73%
Liver Metastases		31	36-58	82,00%	78,00%
Cholangiocarcinoma	TOTAL	56			
	intrahepatic	27	76	68,80%	55,30%
	perihilar	29			
Pancreatic Cancer		64	55.2	82,00%	53,00%
Rectal Cancer		28	73.6	86,00%	92,00%
GENITOURINARY TUMORS					
Prostate Cancer		1247	57.6-63-66	N/A	95.7%
Renal Cell Carcinoma		19	72	94.1%	100,00%
SARCOMA					
Osteosarcoma		79	70.4	62%	33%
Extremity Sarcoma		17	52.8-64-70.4	76%	56%
Sacral Chordoma		95	70.4	88%	86%
CUTANEOUS TUMORS					
Skin Cancer	TOTAL	45			
	Squamous cell carcinoma	16	60-70	90.9%	
	Basal cell carcinoma	12		80.2%	
	Melanoma	7	61-75	85.7%	88.9%
	Bowen's disease	8	60	90%	
	Paget's disease	2	42.5	90%	
Keloids		16	16	N/A	95%

BREAST CANCER					
Breast cancer		7	48-52.8-60	96.3%	100%
GYNECOLOGIC CANCER					
Cervical Cancer		33	68-74.4	71%	88%
Endometrial Cancer		14	62.4-74.4	86%	68%
PAEDIATRIC CANCER					
Paediatric cancer	Osteosarcoma of the trunk	26	70.4	62.9%	50%
	Chordoma or low-grade chondrosarcoma of the skull base	17	60	94%	100%

It will be necessary in the future to develop a separate mathematical model that should confirm correlations between these four attributes, but from the data gathered from previous treatments we can continue with the assumption that following rules will apply:

- Higher number of patients treated will influence the relevance of neuron output, therefore increasing its weight.
- For most organs a higher radiation dose will lead to a higher risk of secondary cancer (with an exception for the thyroid), therefore, dose strength should be minimized, when possible, in particularly for younger patients (children and young adolescents).
- Higher LC rate is in direct correlation with higher overall survival, so its maximization is favorable for hadron therapy eligibility.

The basic idea behind the process of quantification of cancer type and location data is to use categorical data from the ENCR dataset (columns 13_Topo and 14_Morpho) which are expressed in ICD-O-3 codification and add them some quantitative data which are in direct correlation with that type, location, and morphology of cancer. The International Classification of Diseases for Oncology, third edition (ICD-O-3), is designed to categorize tumors. It is used primarily in tumor or cancer registries for coding the site (topography) and the histology (morphology) of neoplasms, usually obtained from a pathology report and in research. The ICD-O-3 is a multiaxial classification, consisting of two main axes, the topography, and the morphology of tumors. For the morphology there exist two additional axes, to differentiate behavior (benign/malignant) and grading of a tumor. The topography axis uses the ICD-10 classification of malignant neoplasms with some exceptions. Behavior and grade of tumor are as well expressed as categorical data in ENCR dataset (columns 15_Beh and 16_Grade).

During data normalization process, ICD-O-3 codification for topology and morphology should be used for selection and calculation of data related to NP, DS, LC, and OC. Output of this calculation should be numerical values for neuron input, bias, and weight, where weight is in direct correlation with NP, and bias with LC and OC.

Figure 5 - Representation of neuron that should quantify tumor topology data

3.5 (G4) Federated Learning environment for data acquisition and aggregation

After further, thorough analysis of the dataset, several problems became evident. First major problem is **data heterogeneity**. Medical data is particularly diverse—not only because of the variety of modalities, dimensionality, and characteristics in general, but even within a specific protocol - due to factors such as acquisition differences, data type and structure, or just local demographics. Cancer patient data are a particular problem, as these data abound in both qualitative and quantitative attributes, which greatly complicates their analysis, calculation of correlation and contingency between attributes. **Data privacy** is next big challenge in FL architecture and of paramount importance when dealing with medical data. Healthcare data is highly sensitive and must be protected accordingly. It is important to note that FL does not solve all potential privacy issues and will always carry some risks. However, there is a trade-off in terms of performance and these techniques may affect, for example, the accuracy of the final model. By definition, FL systems avoid sharing healthcare data among participating institutions. However, the shared information may still indirectly expose private data used for local training, e.g., by model inversion or extraction attacks when adversaries can observe model changes over time, observe specific model updates, like a single institution's data, or even manipulate the model by poisoning data, which is considered an integrity attack because tampering with the training data impacts the model's ability to output correct predictions. And in FL architecture that is much more pronounced, since the poisoning of one participant's model will consequently condition the poisoning of the global model that will be shared with the other members of the federation.

In order to tackle a problem of **data heterogeneity**, we proposed the usage of ENCR dataset. ENCR stands for European Network of Cancer Registries, and it has been in operation since 1990. These datasets follow strict ENCR data format regulations and in addition to that, ENCR are developing software based on the data quality-check protocol, in order to guarantee data consistency. This dataset is composed of independent cancer incident cases, containing anonymized patient data, like their age, sex, type of cancer, morphology, topology, and grade of cancer etc. Problem with this dataset is that it still contains more qualitative than quantitative data, and for ML purposes quantitative data gives much better results. Therefore, in order to solve this problem, we have started analysis of correlation matrixes for quantitative, and contingency tables for qualitative data, and we hope that we'll be able to identify some correlations between these two, in order to be able to combine several attributes in one measurable attribute that can be used in ML algorithms.

As for **Privacy concerns**, several methods have been proposed, like for example usage of homomorphic encryption. This type of encryption permits us to perform computations on encrypted data without first decrypting it, which solves all privacy problems at the cost of increased computation power. Also, we can use Public Key Infrastructure as well, that works with digital certificates and manages public-key encryption.

In the last few months, we also established a communication with Intel, that is developing their own FL framework, and they offered us early access to it and assistance in setting up our first federation. Their FL framework also comes with hardware integration with SGX technology, that stands for Intel Software Guard Extension – and basically is a set of CPU instructions that can be used by applications to set aside private regions of code and data.

3.5.1 OpenFL environment

OpenFL is a Python 3 framework for Federated Learning. OpenFL is designed to be a flexible, extensible, and easily learnable tool for data scientists. OpenFL is developed by Intel Internet of Things Group (IOTG) and Intel Labs.

Figure 6 - Intel OpenFL architecture

Once OpenFL is installed on all nodes of the federation, and every member of the federation has a valid Public Key certificate, all that is needed to run an instance of a federated workload is to distribute the workspace to all federation members, and then run the command to start the node. In other words, most of the work is setting up an initial environment on all federation nodes that can be used federations.

The idea behind all of this is to develop a machine learning system based on Federated Learning technique capable of training a high-quality model with data distributed over several independent providers, several independent oncology institutions in SEEIIST member countries.

The algorithm that demonstrates the entire procedure is:

Require: num_federated_rounds T

1: **procedure** AGGREGATING

2: Initialise global model: $W(0)$

3: **for** $t \leftarrow 1 \dots T$ **do**

4: **for** client $k \leftarrow 1 \dots K$ **do** \triangleright *Run in parallel*

5: Send $W(t - 1)$ to client k

6: Receive model updates and number of local training iterations
 $(\Delta W^{(t-1)}, N_k)$ from client's local training with $L_k(X_k; W^{(t-1)})$

7: **end for**

8: $W^{(t)} \leftarrow W^{(t-1)} + \frac{1}{\sum_k N_k} \sum_k (N_k \cdot W_k^{(t-1)})$

9: **end for**

10: **return** $W(t)$

11: **end procedure**

FL algorithm via Hub & Spoke (Centralised topology) with FedAvg aggregation.

3.5.2 Running the federation

OpenFL currently supports two types of workflows for how to set up and run a federation: Director-based workflow (preferrable) and Aggregator-based workflow (old workflow, will not be supported soon). Director-based workflow introduces a new and more convenient way to set up a federation and brings “long-lived” components in a federation (“Director” and “Envoy”).

- **Director-Based Workflow** - A federation created with this workflow continues to be available to distribute more experiments in series.
- **Aggregator-Based Workflow** - With this workflow, the federation is terminated when the experiment is finished.

On basis of requirements set by the needs of federation that is supposed to connect several hospitals and medical institutions, that will share data without a strict schedule, and therefore cannot depend on each other, I think that we should consider Director based workflow as a desired model.

Director-Based Workflow

A director-based workflow uses long-lived components in a federation. These components continue to be available to distribute more experiments in the federation.

The *Director* is the central node of the federation. This component starts an *Aggregator* for each experiment, sends data to connected collaborator nodes, and provides updates on the status.

The *Envoy* runs on collaborator nodes connected to the *Director*. When the Director starts an experiment, the *Envoy* starts the *Collaborator* to train the global model.

The director-based workflow comprises the following roles and their tasks:

- Director Manager: Sets up the Director - ML model creator’s representative controlling Director
- Collaborator Manager: Set Up the Envoy - Data owner’s representative controlling Envoy
- Experiment Manager: Describe an Experiment - a person or group of people using OpenFL

The OpenFL interactive Python API enables the Experiment manager (data scientists) to define and start a federated learning experiment from a single-entry point: a Jupyter notebook or a Python script.

Figure 7 - Overview of the Director-Based Workflow

After the installation of Open Federated Learning (OpenFL), following steps are necessary for complete federation set up:

Start the Director:

Start the Director on a node with at least two open ports.

Create a Director workspace with a default config file.

```
fx director create-workspace -p path/to/director_workspace_dir
```

This workspace will contain received experiments and supplementary files (Director config file and certificates).

Modify the Director config file according to federation setup.

The default config file contains the Director node FQDN, an open port, path of certificates, and `sample_shape` and `target_shape` fields with string representation of the unified data interface in the federation.

If we decide on a federation with PKI certificates, in order to start a Director it will be necessary to run this command:

```
fx director start -c director_config.yaml \
  -rc cert/root_ca.crt \
  -pk cert/priv.key \
  -oc cert/open.crt
```

Collaborator Manager: Set Up the Envoy

The Collaborator manager sets up the Envoys, which are long-lived components on collaborator nodes. When started, Envoys will try to connect to the Director. Envoys receive an experiment archive and provide access to local data.

In order to create an Envoy workspace with a default config file and shard descriptor Python script, it is necessary to execute following code:

```
fx envoy create-workspace -p path/to/envoy_workspace_dir
```

After the creation of Envoy workspace, it is required to modify the Envoy config file and local shard descriptor template:

- Provide the settings field with the arbitrary settings required to initialize the shard descriptor.
- Complete the shard descriptor template field with the address of the local shard descriptor class.

The shard descriptor is an object to provide a unified data interface for FL experiments. The shard descriptor implements `get_dataset()` method as well as several additional methods to access **sample shape**, **target shape**, and **shard description** that may be used to identify participants during experiment definition and execution.

`get_dataset()` method accepts the `dataset_type` (for instance train, validation, query, gallery) and returns an iterable object with samples and targets.

User's implementation of `ShardDescriptor` should be inherited from `openfl.interface.interactive_api.shard_descriptor.ShardDescriptor`. It should implement `get_dataset`, `sample_shape` and `target_shape` methods to describe the way data samples and labels will be loaded from disk during training.

If we decide on a federation with PKI certificates, in order to start the Envoy, it will be necessary to run this command:

```
ENVOY_NAME=envoy_example_name

fx envoy start \
  -n "$ENVOY_NAME" \
  --envoy-config-path envoy_config.yaml \
  -dh director_fqdn \
  -dp port \
  -rc cert/root_ca.crt \
  -pk cert/"$ENVOY_NAME".key \
  -oc cert/"$ENVOY_NAME".crt
```

Experiment Manager: Describe an Experiment

The process of defining an experiment is decoupled from the process of establishing a federation. The Experiment manager (or data scientist) is able to prepare an experiment in a Python environment. Then the Experiment manager registers experiments into the federation using Interactive Python API that will allow communication with the Director using a gRPC client.

The Open Federated Learning (OpenFL) interactive Python API enables the Experiment manager (data scientists) to define and start a federated learning experiment from a single-entry point: a Jupyter notebook or a Python script.

The Experiment manager requires the following:

- **Python Interpreter**

Create a virtual Python environment with packages required for conducting the experiment. The Python environment is replicated on collaborator nodes.

- **A Local Experiment Workspace**

Initialize a workspace by creating an empty directory and placing inside the workspace a Jupyter* notebook or a Python script. Items in the workspace may include source code of objects imported into the notebook from local modules, local test data stored in a data directory and certificates stored in a cert directory.

This workspace will be archived and transferred to collaborator nodes, so it is necessary to ensure that only relevant source code or resources are stored in the workspace. Data and cert directories will not be included in the archive.

Define a Federated Learning Experiment

The definition process of a federated learning experiment uses the interactive Python API to set up several interface entities and experiment parameters.

The following are the interactive Python API to define an experiment:

- Federation API
- Experiment API
- Start an FL Experiment
- Observe the Experiment Execution

Each federation is bound to some Machine Learning problem in a sense that all collaborators dataset shards should allow to solve the same data science problem.

- Federation API

The Federation entity is designed to be a bridge between a notebook and Director.

First it is necessary to import Federation class from openfl package:

```
from openfl.interface.interactive_api.federation import
Federation
```

Then we need to initialize the Federation object with the Director node network address and encryption settings:

```
federation = Federation(
    client_id: str, director_node_fqdn: str, director_port: str
    tls: bool, cert_chain: str, api_cert: str, api_private_key: str)
```

We have two methods at our disposal in the Federation API:

`get_dummy_shard_descriptor`: creates a dummy shard descriptor for debugging the experiment pipeline

`get_shard_registry`: returns information about the Envoy's connected to the Director and their shard descriptors

- Experiment API

The Experiment entity registers training-related objects, federated learning (FL) tasks, and settings.

First it is necessary to import FLExperiment class from openfl package:

```
from openfl.interface.interactive_api.experiment import
FLExperiment
```

Then, we need to initialize the experiment with the following parameters: a federation object and a unique experiment name.

```
fl_experiment = FLExperiment(federation: Federation,
    experiment_name: str)
```

Import these supplementary interface classes: `TaskInterface`, `DataInterface`, and `ModelInterface`.

```
from openfl.interface.interactive_api.experiment import
TaskInterface, DataInterface, ModelInterface
```

Register the Model and Optimizer (`ModelInterface`)

Instantiate and initialize a model and optimizer in our preferred deep learning framework (The OpenFL interactive API supports TensorFlow and PyTorch frameworks via existing plugins):

```
from openfl.interface.interactive_api.experiment import
ModelInterface

MI = ModelInterface(model, optimizer, framework_plugin: str)
```

The initialized model and optimizer objects should be passed to the `ModelInterface` along with the path to correct Framework Adapter plugin inside the OpenFL package or from local workspace.

Register FL Tasks (`TaskInterface`). An FL task accepts the following objects:

- `model` - will be rebuilt with relevant weights for every task by *TaskRunner*
- `data_loader` - data loader that will provide local data
- `device` - a device to be used for execution on collaborator machines
- `optimizer` (optional) - model optimizer; only for training tasks

Then, it is necessary to register an FL task and accompanying information:

```
TI = TaskInterface()

task_settings = {
    'batch_size': 32,
    'some_arg': 228,
}

@TI.add_kwargs(**task_settings)
@TI.register_fl_task(model='my_model',
                    data_loader='train_loader',
                    device='device', optimizer='my_Adam_opt')
def foo(my_model, train_loader, my_Adam_opt, device, batch_size,
        some_arg=356):
    # training or validation logic
```

FL tasks return a dictionary object with metrics:

```
{metric name: metric value for this task}.
```

The OpenFL interactive API currently allows registering only standalone functions defined in the main module or imported from other modules inside the workspace.

The `TaskInterface` class must be instantiated before you can use its methods to register FL tasks.

- `@TI.register_fl_task()` needs tasks argument names for `model`, `data_loader`, `device`, and `optimizer` (optional) that constitute a task contract. This method adds the callable and the task contract to the task registry.
- `@TI.add_kwargs()` should be used to set up arguments that are not included in the contract.

Register Federated Data Loader (`DataInterface`)

A *shard descriptor* defines how to read and format the local data. Therefore, the *data loader* contains the batching and augmenting data logic, which are common for all collaborators.

Subclass `DataInterface` and implement the following methods.

```
class CustomDataLoader(DataInterface):
    def __init__(self, **kwargs):
        # Initialize superclass with kwargs: this array will be
        # passed
        # to get_data_loader methods
        super().__init__(**kwargs)
        # Set up augmentation, save required parameters,
        # use it as you regular dataset class
        validation_fraction = kwargs.get('validation_fraction',
0.5)
        ...

    @property
    def shard_descriptor(self):
        return self._shard_descriptor

    @shard_descriptor.setter
    def shard_descriptor(self, shard_descriptor):
        self._shard_descriptor = shard_descriptor
        # You can implement data splitting logic here
        # Or update your data set according to Local Shard
        Descriptor attributes if required
```

```
def get_train_loader(self, **kwargs):  
    # these are the same kwargs you provided to __init__,  
    # But passed on a collaborator machine  
    bs = kwargs.get('train_batch_size', 32)  
    return foo_loader()
```

The following are shard descriptor setter and getter methods:

- `shard_descriptor(self, shard_descriptor)` is called during the *Collaborator* initialization procedure with the local shard descriptor. Include in this method any logic that is triggered with the shard descriptor replacement.
- `get_train_loader(self, **kwargs)` is called before the execution of training tasks. This method returns the outcome of the training task according to the `data_loader` contract argument. The `kwargs` dict returns the same information that was provided during the `DataInterface` initialization.
- `get_valid_loader(self, **kwargs)` is called before the execution of validation tasks. This method returns the outcome of the validation task according to the `data_loader` contract argument. The `kwargs` dict returns the same information that was provided during the `DataInterface` initialization.
- `get_train_data_size(self)` returns the number of samples in the local dataset for training. Use the information provided by the shard descriptor to determine how to split your training and validation tasks.
- `get_valid_data_size(self)` returns the number of samples in the local dataset for validation.

- The User Dataset class should be instantiated to pass further to the Experiment object.
- Dummy shard descriptor (or a custom local one) may be set up to test the augmentation or batching pipeline.
- Keyword arguments used during initialization on the frontend node may be used during dataloaders construction on collaborator machines.

- Start an FL Experiment

We will use the Experiment API to prepare a workspace archive to transfer to the Director.

```
FLExperiment.start()
```

Instances of interface

classes `(TaskInterface, DataInterface, ModelInterface)` must be passed to `FLExperiment.start()` method along with other parameters.

This method:

- Compiles all provided settings to a Plan object. The Plan is the central place where all actors in federation look up their parameters.
- Saves **plan.yaml** to the `plan` folder inside the workspace.
- Serializes interface objects on the disk.
- Prepares **requirements.txt** for remote Python environment setup.
- Compresses the whole workspace to an archive.
- Sends the experiment archive to the *Director* so it may distribute the archive across the federation and start the *Aggregator*.

The following are parameters of the `start()` method in FLExperiment:

`model_provider` - This parameter is defined earlier by the `ModelInterface` object.

`task_keeper` - This parameter is defined earlier by the `TaskInterface` object.

`data_loader` - This parameter is defined earlier by the `DataInterface` object.

`rounds_to_train` - This parameter defines the number of aggregation rounds needed to be conducted before the experiment is considered finished.

`delta_updates` - This parameter sets up the aggregation to use calculated gradients instead of model checkpoints.

`opt_treatment` - This parameter defines the optimizer state treatment in the federation.

The following are available values:

- **RESET**: the optimizer state is initialized each round from noise
- **CONTINUE_LOCAL**: the optimizer state will be reused locally by every collaborator
- **CONTINUE_GLOBAL**: the optimizer's state will be aggregated

`device_assignment_policy` - The following are available values:

- **CPU_ONLY**: the `device` parameter (which is a part of a task contract) that is passed to an FL task each round will be `cpu`
- **CUDA_PREFERRED**: the `device` parameter will be `cuda:{index}` if CUDA (Compute Unified Device Architecture) devices are enabled in the Envoy config and `cpu` otherwise.

- Observe the Experiment Execution

If the experiment was accepted by the *Director*, you can oversee its execution with the `FLEXperiment.stream_metrics()` method. This method prints metrics from the FL tasks (and saves TensorBoard logs).

Complete the Experiment

When the experiment has completed:

- retrieve trained models in the native format using `FLEXperiment.get_best_model()` and `FLEXperiment.get_last_model()`.
- erase experiment artifacts from the Director with `FLEXperiment.remove_experiment_data()`.

You may use the same federation object to report another experiment or even schedule several experiments that will be executed in series.

4 Possible biases

Artificial intelligence (AI) has enormous potential in medicine, and this has been recognized by many medical institutions. But growing usage of AI in medicine has brought to surface some potential problems and/or biases that can influence final decision made by AI. In order to avoid such a scenario, here will be listed potential problems that we might encounter during design and development, as well as recommendations for avoiding or solving them.

4.1 Black box modeling

AI decision-making mechanisms depend on patterns in data. On the one hand, the AI learns such patterns in order to mimic human abilities. But, AI can also recognize patterns that remain hidden from humans. The models that result from this process of machine learning are hardly comprehensible. This is mainly because the system creates these models itself through the data it is learning from. The result of this "learning process" is no longer programmed by a human being. In addition, the models are extremely complex. In neural networks, for example, millions of parameters are trained. Therefore, in many cases, AI models are a black box and not understandable even for those who developed them.

As powerful as AI can be, a lack of transparency and explainability can lead to serious errors going undetected or the model becoming unusable. In the worst case scenario, this puts patients at risk. This is why the interpretability of machine learning has to ensure that AI-based (medical) products do not become black boxes. It should allow errors to be identified and security gaps to be avoided. A lack of transparency can mean that the manufacturer does not notice incorrect conclusions of the AI in good time. For example, an AI model does not reliably detect cancer based on suspicious lung tissue but based on the fact that the recordings were commissioned by a specific person such as an oncologist.

As a solution, a procedure should be created that evaluates the relevance of the features (like partial derivatives calculation of the single neuron output) of a machine learning model. This will increase the explainability of the model.

4.2 Survivorship bias

Survivorship bias or survival bias is the logical error of concentrating on the people or things that made it past some selection process and overlooking those that did not, typically because of their lack of visibility. This can lead to some false conclusions in several different ways. Survivorship bias can lead to overly optimistic beliefs because failures are ignored, such as when companies that no longer exist are excluded from analyses of financial performance. It can also lead to the false belief that the successes in a group have some special property, rather than just coincidence (correlation "proves" causality).

For example, if we are taking a sample of people with cancer and add into our model features such as age, time since diagnosis, age when diagnosed, gender, cancer type etc. By doing this we would be ignoring all the people who didn't make it since they were not diagnosed with the disease. These people surely have their own characteristics. We wouldn't know and it would be a huge case of survivorship bias directly stuck into our dataset, and therefore predictions.

In our particular case, cancer patients' dataset has a column 12_BoD (Base od Diagnosis) where 0 describes patients who were diagnosed only after death, and they make only 1.36% of all diagnosed patients. We can only imagine how many more patients were not diagnosed with cancer, and therefore did not make it into the statistics.

In order to prevent survivorship bias, researchers must be very selective with their data sources. We must ensure that the data sources that they have selected do not omit observations that are no longer in existence in order to reduce the risk of survivorship bias.

4.3 Human error biases and data poisoning

Machine-learning models, at their core, are predictive engines. Large data sets train machine-learning models to predict the future based on the past. Models can read masses of text and understand intent, where intent is known. They can learn to spot differences by consuming millions of pieces of data, such as correctly labeled animal photos.

The advantage of machine-learning models over traditional statistical models is their ability to quickly evaluate enormous numbers of records and thereby more accurately make predictions. But since machine-learning models predict exactly what they have been trained to predict, their forecasts are only as good as the data used for their training. For example, machine-learning model used to scan reams of résumés or applications to schools might mistakenly screen out female applicants if the historical data used to train it reflects past decisions that resulted in few women being hired or admitted to a college.

These types of biases are especially pervasive in data sets based on decisions made by a relatively small number of people. As a best practice, supervisors must always keep in mind that if humans are involved in decisions, bias always exists — and the smaller the group, the greater the chance that the bias is not overridden by others.

In our particular case, human error or deliberate data mistreatment is more probable, because data ingestion is performed from multiple entry points (member of the federation). Therefore, data is more susceptible to the personal bias of the person entering the data or making a diagnosis. For example, personal bias on national, religions, sexual or racial level, of single individual in the chain of data entry and management, could influence all other members of the federation, once data has been aggregated and reshared. But these biases don't have to be intentional, some patient's data could be related to some geographical specification. For example, doctors in one country are more likely to treat oncological patients with radiotherapy, because they have resources to do so, or some geographical areas

could be more susceptible to one form of cancer than the other (in the western Balkans in particular, because of usage of impoverished uranium in war operations in the former Yugoslavia).

This is known as data poisoning. It is particularly easy if those involved suspect that they are dealing with a self-learning system, like a recommendation engine. All they need to do is make their attack clever enough to pass the automated data checks—which is not usually very hard. The other issue with data poisoning is that it could be a long, slow process. Hackers can afford to take their time to change the data by feeding in a few results at a time. Indeed, this is often more effective, because it is harder to detect than a massive influx of data at a single point in time—and significantly harder to undo.

Fortunately, there are steps that organisations can take to prevent data poisoning. These include:

1. Establish an end-to-end ModelOps process to monitor all aspects of model performance and data drifts
2. For automatic re-training of models, establish a business flow. This means that model will have to go through a series of checks and validations by different people in the business before the updated version goes live
3. Hire experienced data scientists and analysts. There is a growing tendency to assume that everything technical can be handled by software engineers, especially with the shortage of qualified and experienced data scientists. However, this is not the case. We need experts who really understand AI systems and machine learning algorithms, and who know what to look for when we are dealing with threats like data poisoning
4. Use 'open' with caution. Open-source data are very appealing because they provide access to more data to enrich existing sources. In principle, this should make it easier to develop more accurate models. However, these data are just that: open. This makes them an easy target for fraudsters and hackers.

5 Future objectives

In the following period it is expected to be able to conclude two previously set goals, there were left unfinished because of lack of data:

- Unifying data from various sources and creation of unique dataset in a federated learning environment.
- Creation of machine learning algorithm capable of selecting patients suitable for hadron therapy.

Furthermore, it will be necessary to involve oncologists in our data interpretation and attempts of quantification of categorical data.

- Establish communication with oncologists who will help us define precise outcome of the machine learning process, and help us define algorithm for possible, missing outcomes in our current dataset.
- Next step in machine learning approach to the problem of hadron therapy could be to predict the dose distribution based on the patient anatomy, cancer type and morphology.

For this purpose, a machine learning pipeline has been envisioned, that consists of six steps:

- Data ingestion (Upload data from different sources on the repository and read it);
- Data normalization (Reduce number of columns, quantify data);
- Data Homogenization (Find columns in common. Unify different datasets);
- Model development and distribution (*Fine tune model on a reduced dataset*);
- Dataset training (Train the best model on the entire dataset and explore different prediction algorithms);
- Results visualization (Use of trained data for patients' classification with supervised learning).

Figure 8 - Proposed workflow

For purpose of defining precise outcomes and better understanding importance of existing attributes in the dataset, I have written collaboration project proposal intended for oncologist willing to participate in this research:

Project consists of designing large-scale privacy-preserving data analysis platforms for medical research applications, with emphasis on cancer patients' data. Proposal is to develop a machine learning system based on Federated Learning technique capable of training a high-quality model with data distributed over several independent providers without sharing patients' private data. As predictive models need to be trained on heterogeneous data to generalize well to different patient populations and treatment plans, it was proposed to use datasets collected by European Network of Cancer Registries (ENCR) that are already available, anonymized, and standardized. Final result of this use-case should represent a prediction model capable of suggesting patients suitable for hadron therapy.

This dataset is composed of independent cancer incident cases, containing anonymized patient data, like their age, sex, type of cancer, morphology, topology, behavior, and grade of cancer, proposed classical therapy methods etc. Problem with this dataset is that it still contains more qualitative than quantitative data, and for machine learning purposes quantitative data gives much better results. In order to quantify given data, several methods have been proposed:

- Association of several attributes (quantitative and qualitative), in order to be able to obtain one measurable attribute (coefficient). For example, cancer topology, its grade and age of the patient, or tumor type, morphology, and size.
- Furthermore, as “cancer type” has too broad meaning to be left as a single attribute, idea is to quantify it by using several other quantitative attributes that could be obtained from publication on proton, helium, and hadron therapy. Those attributes would be number of patients treated, LC (local control) rate, Gray Equivalent (GyE) dose, and overall survival (OS).

As both above-mentioned methods reside well outside of my area of expertise, and at the same time represent critical ethical and oncological problem, that I cannot, and must not define alone, I am looking for help from renowned experts in fields of oncology and hadron cancer therapy, that would help me define and quantify attributes from cancer patient's dataset. In other words, I would require help in deciding on level of “importance” of these data, and their impact on final decision of patient's suitability for hadron therapy.

Furthermore, in order to generate output with reasonable accuracy, and to be able to “learn”, machine learning algorithm requires that dataset used for its training contains already output for every single patient. This means that it is necessary to add another column to ENCR dataset, containing data of suitability of that patient for hadron therapy (from 0% to 100%), or at least binary option (0 – not suitable, 1 – suitable). As I don't expect anyone to go through 3000 patients records and decide on every single patient's suitability, it would be a good start to input data for at least 5-10% of patients, in order to cover all cancer types, as

well as age and sex groups. This way it would be easier to explain criteria and methodology for patients' selection, which would help us devise an algorithm that would generate coefficients for all remaining patients in the dataset.

Artificial intelligence shows great potential to streamline the treatment planning process in heavy ion therapy. However, its clinical adoption is slow due to the limited number of clinical evaluation studies and because often, the translation of the predicted dose distribution to a deliverable plan is lacking. The process of treatment planning is manual and iterative, which can be time consuming. In recent years, several methods have been developed to automate this process, including machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) approaches⁷⁰. Most studies focus on the treatment sites like prostate, head and neck, or breast, but with increasing number of patients with other cancer types that have been treated in hadron facilities we can extend our field of research even further.

As usage of machine learning represents completely new approach to a very common problem of patients' selection process and their categorization for specific medical treatments, I am certain that research in this direction could be very fruitful.

⁷⁰ Meyer P, Biston MC, Khamphan C, Marghani T, Mazurier J, Bodez V, et al. Automation in radiotherapy treatment planning: examples of use in clinical practice and future trends for a complete automated workflow. *Cancer Radiother.* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.canrad.2021.06.006>.